

**Migrant
Integration through
Locally designed
Experiences**

The inclusion of migrants in policy making

A report on the European Union

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Contents

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT	2
EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	4
1 THE EUROPEAN CONTEXT OF MIGRATION	7
2 THE EU GOVERNANCE AND MIGRATION AND DIVERSITY POLICY	15
3 THE EVOLUTION OF INCLUSIVITY OF MIGRANTS IN POLICY MAKING.....	27
4 ENGAGEMENT OF MIGRANT COMMUNITIES IN POLICY MAKING	50
REFERENCES.....	76
APPENDIX – List of primary data sources.....	77

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report provides research evidence on the inclusion of international migrants – and in particular so-called ‘third country nationals’ (TCN) – in policy making in the European Union (EU), with a specific focus on the existing equality, diversity, integration and civic participation policy and practice in the region as well as capturing progress over time.

The EU is a unique economic and political union between 27 European countries. The EU has 447.7 million inhabitants. Germany, France and Italy together compose nearly half (47%) of the total EU population. As of 2021, there were 23.7 million non-EU citizens (5.3% of EU's total population) and 37.5 million people born outside the EU (8.4% of all EU population), whereas 13.7 million people living in one of the EU Member States with the citizenship of another EU Member State. The proportion of inhabitants born outside the EU has overall increased in recent years, but the increase varies widely across Member States.

At the end of 2020, most of the non-EU citizens residing in the EU with a valid residence permit had obtained residency because of family or work reasons. In turn, the share of refugees in the EU was about 0.6% of its total population.

The EU operates as a single market of 27 countries, whose total gross domestic value in 2019 was about €16.4 trillion. Along with China and the United States, it is amongst the three largest actors in international trade. The labour market performance varies across EU countries and regions, with structural weaknesses in some countries: within single EU Member States, there are often large differences in employment rates between regions. In 2020, in the EU, 18.3 million of all employees (around 8% of the total) were migrants: half from another EU country, and half from a third country. In general, employment rates for migrants and in particular for refugees and asylum-seekers are 15% lower on average than those of EU native-born population.

In the EU economy, COVID-19 pandemic acted as a watershed, plunging the EU into its worst-ever recession. The war following the Russian invasion of Ukraine is having relevant consequences on the EU economy too, especially on the energy sector.

The governance of migration and diversity at EU level differs when we speak of intra-European migrants or EU nationals; extra-European migrants or Third Country Nationals (TCNs); and migrants seeking international protection. The EU and its Member States share the competence in the area of migration. The EU provides common procedures and rights whereas the national level is still the relevant sovereign entity for the management of entries. The free circulation of EU nationals across Member States is provided by the Schengen intergovernmental agreement (1985). Asylum seekers and refugees are also a shared competence of the EU and Member States, and their entrances are regulated by the Common European Asylum System (CEAS), first adopted in 1999 and reformed in 2020. The European Union Agency for Asylum (EUAA) contributes to improving the functioning and implementation of the CEAS. In September 2020, the

Commission proposed the New Pact on Asylum and Migration aimed at providing a comprehensive common European framework for migration and asylum management.

Officially, the EU does not have an integration policy. The responsibility for integration policies lies primarily with Member States. The new EU Action Plan on Integration and Inclusion (2021-2027) was launched by the European Commission, clarifying that national governments are primarily responsible for the design of integration and social policies (education, employment, housing, healthcare), whereas the EU plays a fundamental role in supporting them and other stakeholders through funding, developing practical tools, coordinating actions and establishing relevant partnerships. Funds related to migration and integration policies are the Asylum, Migration and Integration fund (AMIF) to support early integration, European Social Fund Plus (ESF+), European Regional Development Fund (ERDF), Erasmus+, and the European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development (EAFRD) to support medium and long-term integration.

In general, the EU institutions appear to be moving towards an intersectional approach in seeking to tackle multiple axes of inequality simultaneously. This transpires in the adoption of a series of strategies, including the Gender Equality Strategy (2020-2025); the LGBTIQ Equality Strategy 2020-2025; the EU Anti-Racism Action Plan 2020-2025; and the Roma Strategic framework on equality, inclusion and participation 2020-2030. The new EU Action Plan on Integration and Inclusion asserts that gender, racial or ethnic origin, religion or belief, sexual orientation and disability will be a focus for the integration and inclusion of migrant persons.

In the European context, when we talk about local participation of residents *in general*, we refer to the EU Cohesion Policy, which represents almost a third of the total EU budget (EUR 372 billion for 2021-2027) and one of the EU's largest investment policies. The instruments and funds of the Cohesion Policy were used to welcome the high number of people fleeing from Ukraine following the Russian invasion, with the Cohesion's Action for Refugees in Europe (CARE) of over 370 billion Euros of cohesion funds, supporting states and regions by providing emergency assistance to people fleeing from Russia's invasion of Ukraine.

The participation of TCNs is still stuttering. Before they acquire EU citizenship, TCNs have no right to vote for the European Parliament. However, there exists wide consultations regarding EU migration and integration policies, such as the consultation which took place before the new EU Action Plan, or "Ask the People", organised by the European Migrant Advisory Board (EMAB).

At the EU level, TCNs can take part in expert groups and advisory boards. Two in particular deserve attention when it comes to the inclusion of TCNs in EU policy making: the European Migrant Advisory Board (EMAB) set by the Urban Agenda for the EU Partnership on Inclusion of Migrants and Refugees (2016-2019), and the Expert Group on the views of migration, asylum and integration with the EC, set at the start of the new EU Action Plan on Integration and Inclusion (2021-2027). Dissemination of information about the possibility to participate occurs through various channels, either news of the official

websites, newsletters sent to mailing lists open to subscription, social media (Facebook and Twitter) and then national contact points and their networks.

There is no coordination mechanism at the EU level to ensure that participation of all residents is actively promoted and communicated effectively. Interviews show that intersectionality is not taken into account to enhance participation, and participants in boards and expert groups are either civil servants, academics or consultants who can bear the weight of these unpaid meetings and the preparation before them. For those who do manage to access EU institutions, migrants' engagement in EU policy making is often limited to recommendations without any follow-up. Informal forms of institutional interaction exist but largely depend on MEPs' sensitivity, will and interests in the topic. At the European Parliament level, there is no stable and regular practice, nor fully established mechanisms, to ensure institutional responsiveness to migrants' requests.

Key migrant-led organisations across the EU have a better chance at being heard. Among these organisations are refugee-led, migrant-led, migrant women-led, second generation/youth-led, and other migration-related diversity. Only 25% of all migrant-led organisations within European countries are members of EU-level or international-level umbrella organisations. Some examples are the European Network against Racism (ENAR) with 10 organisations, the European Network of Migrant Women (ENoMW) with 7 structures, the Union Migrant Network, or the Platform for International Cooperation on Undocumented Migrants (PICUM).

New treaties, common policies and EU enlargements are significant milestones in the change of the legal framework of migration and integration, the diversification of the European Parliament, the weight of voters, and because groups of migrants that were previously outside of the EU (and hence, TCNs) have become EU nationals. In 2015, the so-called "refugee crisis" reached its peak and triggered a migration governance crisis in the EU. The principle of solidarity established in Maastricht and the Dublin system were both put in question. The Urban Agenda for the EU Partnership on Inclusion of Migrants and Refugees (2016-2019), the new EU Action Plan on Integration and Inclusion (2021-2027), and the New Pact on Migration and Asylum (2024) are responses to this governance crisis. In general, there has been an increased attention towards participation and inclusion of migrants in policy-making, which is reflected in decisions related to the EU funding allocation.

1 THE EUROPEAN CONTEXT OF MIGRATION

1.1 The European context

European Union. The European Union (EU) is a unique economic and political union between 27 European countries, which began as a purely economic union to evolve into an organisation spanning many different policy areas, including justice and migration. Some values are common to the Member States (MS) and are an integral part of the European way of life: pluralism, non-discrimination, tolerance, justice, solidarity and equality between women and men prevail.

Economy. The EU operates as a single market of 27 countries, whose total gross domestic value in 2019 was about €16.4 trillion. Along with China and the United States, it is amongst the three largest actors in international trade. All the EU Member States are part of the Economic and Monetary Union (EMU). In 1999, 19 Member States replaced their national currencies with a single currency, the euro, becoming part of the euro area and further integrating their economies. If economic policy largely remains the domain of the Member States - who must coordinate their economic policies to reach the common goals of stability, growth and employment, and agree on rules for fiscal discipline - the monetary policy in the euro area is the responsibility of the European Central Bank.¹ Since 2011, the European Semester is the framework through which surveillance and coordination of economic and employment policies across the Union occurs. Here, EU countries' fiscal, economic and employment policy challenges are discussed.

Labour market and entrepreneurial activity. The performance of labour markets varies between EU countries and regions, in some countries showing structural weaknesses. Indeed, rural or peripheral regions present some of the lowest regional employment rates in the EU, for instance in southern Spain and southern Italy, Greece, the outermost regions of France, and many of the rural areas in eastern Europe. Conversely, some of the highest regional employment rates in 2020 were concentrated in southern Germany. It is interesting to note that within single EU Member States, there are often large differences in employment rates between regions: for instance, Bulgaria, Croatia, Lithuania, Hungary, Poland, Slovenia and Slovakia have the highest employment rate in their capital region; conversely, Belgium and Austria have the lowest one in the capital region.²

In 2021, the EU population reached 446.947 million; of this, around 216.788 million people - corresponding to the 48.5% - are part of the labour force.³ In the second quarter

¹ European Commission (2022) 'What is the Euro area?', Available at: https://economy-finance.ec.europa.eu/euro/what-euro-area_en [Accessed on 31/08/2022]

² Eurostats Statistics Explained (2022) 'Labour market statistics at regional level', Available at: https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Labour_market_statistics_at_regional_level#Employment [Accessed on 31/08/2022]

³ The World Bank Data (2022) 'Labor force, total - European Union' and 'Population, total - European Union', Available at: <https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/SL.TLF.TOTL.IN?locations=EU> [Accessed on 25/11/22]

of 2022, the employment rate of the working age population (20-64 years) was around 74.8% (more specifically around 80% for men and 70% for women), unemployment rate around 6%, and labour market slack around 11.5%.⁴ During the pandemic, a majority of the EU Member States saw their unemployment rates rise, with some exceptions (Poland, France, Italy and Greece). When talking about unemployment, a special mention has to be made to youth unemployment rates, particularly high in southern Europe and largely peripheral regions. Employment policies are in the hands of member states, however, the EU aims at better coordinating them, for instance, by providing country-specific recommendations on how to boost jobs and growth.

Regarding the entrepreneurial activity in the EU, the self-employment indicates the percentage of self-employed workers over total employment: in 2020, self-employment EU value is 13.3%, from around 5% in Norway to around 28% in Greece.⁵ In 2022, the EU has approximately 23.2 million enterprises operating in the non-financial business economy.⁶ In 2019, Eurostat registered that the overwhelming majority of enterprises forming part of the non-financial business economy in the EU were micro or small-sized enterprises; however, this percentage was not reflected in terms of their contribution to value added or employment.⁷

TCNs in the European labour market and entrepreneurial activity. In 2020, in the EU, 18.3 million of all employees (around 8% of the total) were migrants: half from another EU country, and half from a third country).⁸ Moreover, the number of TCNs entering the EU labour market has been increasing every year; this rising number stopped with the beginning of the pandemic.⁹ As the 2021 study conducted by the European Parliamentary Research Service states,¹⁰ in general, employment rates for migrants and in particular for refugees and asylum-seekers are persistently lower than those of EU native-born population. In 2021, the average employment rate in the working age population (aged

⁴ Eurostats Statistics Explained (2022) 'EU labour market - quarterly statistics', Available at: https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=EU_labour_market_-_quarterly_statistics#Labour_market_slack_decreased_the_most_in_Ireland.2C_Latvia.2C_Greece.2C_Italy_and_Slovenia [Accessed on 31/08/2022]

⁵ CEDEFOP (2022) 'Self-employment', Available at: <https://www.cedefop.europa.eu/en/tools/skills-intelligence/self-employment?year=2020&country=EU#1> [Accessed on 25/11/2022]

⁶ Statista (2022) 'Number of enterprises in the non-financial business economy of the European Union (EU27) from 2008 to 2022', Available at: <https://www.statista.com/statistics/1248775/number-of-businesses-eu/> [Accessed on 31/08/2022].

⁷ Eurostat (2022) 'EU small and medium-sized enterprises: an overview', Available at: <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/products-eurostat-news/-/edn-20220627-1> [Accessed on 25/11/2022]

⁸ International Centre for Migration Policy Development ICMPD (2020) 'Labour migration - Five priorities for the EU and its Member States', Available at: <https://www.icmpd.org/news/labour-migration-five-priorities-for-the-eu-and-its-member-states> [Accessed on: 05/10/2022]

⁹ *Ibid.*

¹⁰ European Parliamentary Research Service (2021) 'Labour market integration of asylum-seekers and refugees', Available at: [https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/BRIE/2021/690651/EPRS_BRI\(2021\)690651_EN.pdf](https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/BRIE/2021/690651/EPRS_BRI(2021)690651_EN.pdf) [Accessed on 05/10/2022]

20 to 64 years) of EU citizens was 74%, compared to the 59.1% of non-EU citizens.¹¹ This gap is stronger in EU Nordic countries and in long-standing immigration destinations.¹²

If we focus more specifically on the employment rate of the population aged 20-64 years in 2020 in the partner countries participating in MILE, comparing native-born and non-EU born population, we find that: in Belgium, the employment rate for the native-born population is 72.6% compared to 52.3 for the non-EU born population; in Greece, 61.8% compared to 53.3%; in Latvia, 77.6% compared to 71.2%; in the Netherlands, 82,3% compared to 64,2%; in Spain, 67,1% compared to 58.6%;¹³ and in the UK, 76.4% compared to 72%.¹⁴

According to a 2019 joint publication by the Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) and the European Commission (EC),¹⁵ immigrants (defined in this study as the foreign-born population, meaning all people born outside the country in which they are resident, with no differences between those born in another EU country and those born in a third country) - in particular TCNs - hold 25% of low-skilled jobs: indeed, they tend to be employed in low-skilled jobs with high automation potential in the future, and therefore in roles likely to decline. For this reason, facilitating the recognition of migrants' qualifications and upgrading their education and skills will be vital.¹⁶ As the joint publication makes clear, overqualification of immigrants represents an issue: of the 11 million of immigrants in the EU who are considered highly educated, 2.9 million have a job for which they are overqualified and 2.4 million are unemployed. As a result, in EU countries, the employment rate of TCNs with foreign credentials is 14 percentage points lower than the rate of their peers with host-country qualifications.

In terms of sectors, relying on data from 2020, TCNs are overrepresented in the accommodation and food services activities, administrative and support activities,

¹¹ European Commission (2022) 'Statistics on migration to Europe', Available at: https://ec.europa.eu/info/strategy/priorities-2019-2024/promoting-our-european-way-life/statistics-migration-europe_en#employment-of-immigrants [Accessed on 28/11/2022]

¹² European Parliamentary Research Service (2021) 'Labour market integration of asylum-seekers and refugees', Available at: [https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/BRIE/2021/690651/EPRS_BRI\(2021\)690651_EN.pdf](https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/BRIE/2021/690651/EPRS_BRI(2021)690651_EN.pdf) [Accessed on 05/10/2022]

¹³ Eurostat (2022) 'Migrant integration statistics labour market indicators', Available at: https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Migrant_integration_statistics_-_labour_market_indicators#Employment_rates [Accessed on 28/11/2022]

¹⁴ Clark, D. (2022) 'Employment rate of UK and non-UK born adults in the UK 1997-2022', Available at: <https://www.statista.com/statistics/915732/immigrant-employment-rate-uk/> [Accessed on 28/11/2022]

¹⁵ OECD / European Union (2018) 'Settling in 2018: Indicators of immigrant integration', OECD Publishing, Paris/European Union, Brussels, (p. 88), Available at: <https://www.oecd-ilibrary.org/docserver/9789264307216-en.pdf?expires=1662889868&id=id&accname=guest&checksum=99D883BF15B1EC779B289D9D73D98A45> [Accessed on 11/09/2022]

¹⁶ European Parliamentary Research Service (2021) 'Labour market integration of asylum-seekers and refugees', Available at: [https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/BRIE/2021/690651/EPRS_BRI\(2021\)690651_EN.pdf](https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/BRIE/2021/690651/EPRS_BRI(2021)690651_EN.pdf) [Accessed on 05/10/2022]

domestic work and construction. Conversely, they are underrepresented mainly in public administration and defence, and education.¹⁷

In the EU, on average, around 12% of immigrants in employment are self-employed (defined as people who work in their own firms or create their own businesses, as entrepreneurs, liberal professionals, artisans, traders, freelancers), reaching the same rate of the native-born population. More specifically, having a look at MILE's partners, in Spain, the percentage of immigrant population and native-born one are similar, both around 15%; in Belgium, it is 12% for the native-born and 14% for the immigrant; in the Netherlands, both percentages are around 14%; in Latvia, both percentages are around 10%. For the UK and Greece, the differences are more evident: in the UK, the percentage for the native-born population is around 13%, whereas 17% for the immigrant population; in Greece, the percentage is 24% of the native born and 12% for the immigrant population. In general, especially in Central and Eastern Europe, immigrants are more likely to be self-employed than their native-peers. This is true for more settled migrants: indeed, lower rates of self-employment are present among more recent immigrants.¹⁸

Research demonstrates that migration flows contribute to the European labour market by filling gaps in low and high-skilled occupations, addressing labour market imbalances, contributing more in taxes than they receive in terms of benefits, spurring innovation and consequently economic growth.¹⁹

Finally, it is important to consider irregular foreign employment, which represents about 1.1% of the total EU labour force, or 2.4 million irregular migrant workers.²⁰ They fill some key gaps in the European labour market, being employed mainly in domestic work, construction, small trade, catering industry, tourism, harvesting and seasonal work. As is known, the key role played by this category of workers became evident during the pandemic and the restrictions to mobility that followed its outbreak.

Crises. In the EU economy, COVID-19 pandemic acted as a watershed, plunging the EU into its worst-ever recession. Indeed, the pandemic's outbreak ended a period of six

¹⁷ European Parliamentary Research Service (2021) 'Labour market integration of asylum-seekers and refugees', Available at: [https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/BRIE/2021/690651/EPRS_BRI\(2021\)690651_EN.pdf](https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/BRIE/2021/690651/EPRS_BRI(2021)690651_EN.pdf) [Accessed on 05/10/2022]

¹⁸ OECD / European Union (2018) 'Settling in 2018: Indicators of immigrant integration', OECD Publishing, Paris/European Union, Brussels, (p. 88), Available at: <https://www.oecd-ilibrary.org/docserver/9789264307216-en.pdf?expires=1662889868&id=id&accname=guest&checksum=99D883BF15B1EC779B289D9D73D98A45> [Accessed on 11/09/2022]

¹⁹ European Parliamentary Research Service (2021) 'Labour market integration of asylum-seekers and refugees', (p.4), Available at: [https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/BRIE/2021/690651/EPRS_BRI\(2021\)690651_EN.pdf](https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/BRIE/2021/690651/EPRS_BRI(2021)690651_EN.pdf) [Accessed on 05/10/2022]

²⁰ International Centre for Migration Policy Development ICMPD (2020) 'Labour migration - Five priorities for the EU and its Member States', Available at: <https://www.icmpd.org/news/labour-migration-five-priorities-for-the-eu-and-its-member-states> [Accessed on 05/10/2022].

consecutive years of increases for the EU's employment rate and had a considerable and asymmetric impact on all EU labour markets. Thanks to innovative policy responses and common financial instruments, growth has been relaunched.²¹ The war following the Russian invasion of Ukraine is having relevant consequences on the EU economy, especially on the energy sector.²² Indeed, following the beginning of the war, there has been a sharp increase in energy prices, and concerns regarding the security of energy supply in the EU have arisen. As a consequence, EU leaders have soon agreed to work towards EU's independence from Russian fossil fuels. Moreover, the war is directly affecting global food security and affordability, to which the EU is well responding thanks to its Common Agricultural Policy (CAP).

Population. The EU has 447.7 million inhabitants.²³ On 1 January 2020, Germany, France and Italy together composed nearly half (47%) of the total EU population. Analysing EU demographic trends is an interesting exercise in order to evaluate the impact that the arrival of non-EU migrants has already had or may have in the future. Indeed, in 2020, the EU witnessed the interruption of a long growth led by a positive net migration; the negative natural change outnumbered the positive net migration.

European Parliament. The European Parliament (EP) which represents the EU's citizens and is directly elected by them is composed of 705 Members (MEPs). MEPs are not organised by nationality but by political affiliation. Indeed, MEPs are divided into 7 political groups, and some of them are known as non-attached Members. In order of composition, they are: group of the European People's Party (EPP) (179); group of the Progressive Alliance of Socialists and Democrats in the EP (S&D) (146); Renew Europe group (98); group of the Greens/European Free Alliance (73); Identity and Democracy (ID) (70); European Conservatives and Reformists (ECR) (63); The Left (39). In order to prepare the EP's plenary sittings, MEPs are divided up among some specialised standing committees, who meet once or twice a month and whose debates are public. The Committee on Civil Liberties, Justice and Home Affairs (LIBE) is the one dealing with migration issues.

1.2 Migrant population and migration history

1.2.1 Migrant population and migration trends

²¹ BusinessEurope (2022) 'BusinessEurope Economic Outlook Summer 2022', Available at: <https://www.buressurope.eu/publications/buressurope-economic-outlook-summer-2022-european-businesses-face-difficult-period> [Accessed on 31/08/2022]

²² European Council (2022) 'Impact of Russia's invasion of Ukraine on the markets: EU response', Available at: <https://www.consilium.europa.eu/en/policies/eu-response-ukraine-invasion/impact-of-russia-s-invasion-of-ukraine-on-the-markets-eu-response/> [Accessed on 11/09/2022]

²³ Eurostats Statistics Explained (2022) 'Population and population change statistics', Available at: https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Population_and_population_change_statistics#EU_population_shows_a_slight_decrease_in_2020 [Accessed on 11/08/2022]

EU Member States have different definitions, categorisations and consequently different statistics capturing migration. In the description hereafter, we will mainly focus on the non-European migrant population and migration history (in reference to EU enlargements, the reader can refer to the timeline in section 3.1 of this report).

In order to understand the current situation in relation to migration, the six key periods of migration that have shaped Europe since World War (WW) II need to be described.²⁴

- *Post-war forced migration*: Europe has been a land of emigration before and between the two WWs. Yet after WWII, the European continent was affected by large population displacements, where peace treaties and the reshaping of the region accompanied a forced migration from East to West.
- *Guestworker policies*: Labour shortage required the recruitment of manpower, notably guest-worker and colonial migrants. By the mid-1950s, continental European countries established bilateral guest-worker agreements, first with Southern Europe, then with Turkey and finally with North Africa, temporarily welcoming labour migrants. In some cases, strict ties between some origins and some destinations occurred due to their colonial past. This period was characterised by a favourable political climate towards international migration. After 1973, all receiving countries ended labour migration and the receiving countries tried to encourage return migration, and started to implement stricter migration policies.
- *Family reunion*: By admitting young men in the 1950s and 1960s, European states committed themselves to admitting their spouses, children and grandparents in the following decades. The foreign population stock continued to grow, reaching 16.4 million (=4.6%) in 1990. Moreover, in the short to medium-term, migrants almost always had a higher birth rate than indigenous population. Multicultural and multilingual societies emerged in Europe. As permanent migration to Europe was unexpected and unwanted, integration policies developed belatedly and inadequately. At the end of the 1970s, immigration flows towards the traditional emigration countries of Southern and Northern Europe began.
- *Cold war induced refugees*: After the 1980s (especially post-1989), Europe witnessed a surge in asylum seekers, with the majority of refugees coming from the Union of Soviet Socialist Republics (USSR) and Eastern Europe. This led Western countries to rapidly establish strict controls on migration. Since the end of the 1970s for Northern Europe, and the end of the 1980s for the South, all major European countries have become migration receiving countries and have had to make policies to promote the integration and inclusion of immigrants. Political considerations became more important in EU countries along with the fear of an

²⁴ Hansen, R. (2003) 'Migration to Europe since 1945: Its history and its lessons', *The Political Quarterly* 74: 25-38. See the introduction, and sixth chapter of Simon, P., Bonifazi, C., Okólski, M., & Schoorl, J. (2008) *International migration in Europe: New trends and new methods of analysis* (p. 344), Amsterdam University Press.

invasion of migrants from the former socialist countries. However, the size of actual flows from East to West has largely been below the levels feared. New forms of mobility have developed, and European migration became much more diverse.

- *High skilled migration and securitization of migration*: At the turn of the new century, some EU countries started paying greater attention to the promotion of skilled migrations, and employment-related migration was generally increasing. The final document²⁵ of the Tampere Conference of 1999 - at the occasion of which the Common European Asylum System (CEAS) was established - contained the basis for a new approach to migration issues at a European level: it calls for considering the positive effects of the flows on the economic development of the sending countries, and on the economies and demography of the countries of arrival. Moreover, the topic of undocumented migration also entered the international stage. A general process of criminalization of migration took place to discourage irregular migration. EU countries, through specific funds and policies towards immediate neighbours to Europe, have attempted to “externalise” border controls towards the Maghreb countries by pressuring North African countries to clamp down on irregular migration.
- *2015 EU governance crisis, or so called “refugee crisis”*: The year 2015 marked a peak in the arrival of refugees, with over 1 million persons arriving in Europe to seek international protection. This was a crucial moment of a longer process that had started with the increasing instability and unrest, and regime changes, throughout the Arab world, which caused mass fluxes towards Europe and significant internal displacements.²⁶ While mostly Syrians, escaping the Syrian civil war, persons from the Balkan, Afghanistan and Nigeria (Boko Haram insurgency) also made the ranks of the newcomers. The crossing through the “Aegean Sea route”, and then through the Balkans was lethal and many died on the way. Several EU Member States responded by rebordering. Beyond the humanitarian crisis, these tragic events led to an EU governance crisis, to which the EU responded with a series of controversial mechanisms, such as the EU-Turkey refugee return agreement.²⁷ In 2016, the EC began reforming the CEAS asylum system²⁸. At the same time, a reinforcement of the role of cities, and of networks of cities, is also evident.²⁹

²⁵ European Parliament (1999) ‘TAMPERE EUROPEAN COUNCIL 15 AND 16 OCTOBER 1999 - PRESIDENCY CONCLUSIONS’, Available at: https://www.europarl.europa.eu/summits/tam_en.htm [Accessed in 08/2022]

²⁶ Kingsley, P. (2015) ‘Arab spring prompts biggest migrant wave since second world war’, *The Guardian*, Available at: <https://www.theguardian.com/world/commentisfree/2015/jan/03/arab-spring-migrant-wave-instability-war> [Accessed on 20/09/2022]

²⁷ European Parliament (2022) ‘Legislative train. EU-Turkey Statement and Action Plan’, Available at: <https://www.europarl.europa.eu/legislative-train/carriage/eu-turkey-statement-action-plan/report?sid=6101> [Accessed in 06/2022]

²⁸ European Commission (2022) ‘Common European Asylum System’, Available at: https://home-affairs.ec.europa.eu/policies/migration-and-asylum/common-european-asylum-system_en [Accessed in 06/2022]

²⁹ Lacroix, T. (2021) ‘Migration-related city networks: a global overview’, *Local Government Studies*, 1-21.

Forced migration to Europe continues from the Middle-East, sub-Saharan Africa (to the Canary Islands for instance), Afghanistan, with high levels of lethality. New routes were made more visible, including a scheme organised by the Belarus government, and leading to the death of many on their way to Poland between August to December 2021.³⁰ In February 2022, the declaration of war of Russia to Ukraine triggered mass migration: in June 2022, there were 5.5 million Ukrainian refugees in Europe, 3.6 million having received temporary protection.³¹

As of 2021, there were 23.7 million non-EU citizens (5.3% of EU's total population) and 37.5 million people born outside the EU (8.4% of all EU population), whereas 13.7 million people living in one of the EU Member States with the citizenship of another EU Member State (2021).³² The proportion of inhabitants born outside the EU has overall increased in recent years, but the increase varies widely across Member States, with 10% or above of the resident population in Sweden, Latvia, Estonia, Luxembourg, Croatia, Latvia, Austria, Malta and Germany, and below 3% in Czechia, Hungary, Romania, Bulgaria, Poland and Slovakia.³³

As data of the Commission state,³⁴ at the end of 2020 most of the non-EU citizens resident in the EU with a valid residence permit had obtained it because of family or work reasons, and Ukrainian, Moroccan and India were the top three nationalities of first residence permits. Moreover, the share of refugees in the EU was about 0.6% of its total population. In addition, the top three nationalities of first time asylum applicants in 2021 were Syrian, Afghan and Iraqi, and most of them were lodged in Germany, France, Spain, Italy and Austria.

1.2.2 Civil society and migrant-led organisations in the EU

There are a number of large migrant-run organisations, or those supporting migrants, that operate and collaborate at the international level. For instance, OXFAM, New Women Connectors, the European Council on Refugees and Exiles, the European Network Against Racism, and the European Network of Migrant Women were part of the consulted organisations for the drafting³⁵ of the Action Plan for Integration and Inclusion 2021-2027

³⁰ Fatahi Faz Abad, K. I. (2022) 'Weapons of Mass Migration in the 21st Century: Russia, Belarus, and the European Union', Senior Theses. 98, Available at: https://research.library.fordham.edu/international_senior/98

³¹ UNHCR (2022), 'Ukraine Refugee Situation', available at: <https://data.unhcr.org/en/situations/ukraine> [accessed in 06/2022].

³² European Commission (2022) 'Statistics on Migration to Europe', available at: https://ec.europa.eu/info/strategy/priorities-2019-2024/promoting-our-european-way-life/statistics-migration-europe_en [accessed in 06/2022].

³³ European Commission (2020) 'Action plan on Integration and Inclusion 2021-2027', available at: [https://home-affairs.ec.europa.eu/system/files_en?file=2020-11/action_plan_on_integration_and_inclusion_2021-2027.pdf](https://home-affairs.ec.europa.eu/system/files/en?file=2020-11/action_plan_on_integration_and_inclusion_2021-2027.pdf), p. 2 [accessed in 06/2022].

³⁴ European Commission (2022) 'Statistics on migration to Europe', available at: https://ec.europa.eu/info/strategy/priorities-2019-2024/promoting-our-european-way-life/statistics-migration-europe_en [accessed in 07/2022].

³⁵ European Commission (2020) 'Report on the consultation on the integration and inclusion of migrants and people with a migrant background', Available at: <https://home->

- a plan we will mention often in this report. Expert groups consulted by the Commission involve individuals as well as civil society organisations. For instance, the Expert Group on the views of Migrants (created in 2020) includes 12 organisations from the Civil Society³⁶ acting at the international level, such as Platform for International Cooperation on Undocumented Migrants (PICUM); the European level, such as Save the Children Europe; or at the national level, such as Migrant Women Association Malta (MWAM). However, as sources from the European Parliament state, the awareness of the existence of a European network of migrants that represents migrants' interests and advocates for their rights does not reach the institutional level, and consequently is not seen as an interlocutor by European institutions (interview 5).

2 THE EU GOVERNANCE AND MIGRATION AND DIVERSITY POLICY

2.1 Governance structure and EU decision-making powers

The governance of the European Union (EU) is inherited from the European Economic Community and Euratom created in the 1950s. Through a series of treaties, it has acquired a complex yet stable institutional system. Today, it is constituted by seven main institutions.³⁷

- the **European Commission** (EC) is the main executive body of the EU and represents EU's common interests. It has the right of initiative; then, its proposals for new laws are scrutinised and adopted by the European Parliament and the Council of the EU. The Commission also manages EU policies (except for the Common Foreign and Security Policy, which is conducted by the High Representative for CFSP, Vice-President of the European Commission) and the EU's budget, and it ensures that Member States apply EU law correctly.
- in the **European Council** the heads of state or government of the EU Member States meet to define the general political direction and priorities of the EU. Chaired by a president who is elected every 2.5 years (renewable once), it does not adopt laws except for possible EU Treaty amendments.
- the **Council of the European Union** (also called **Council**) represents the governments of EU Member States and takes decisions on European laws jointly with the EP. Here, national ministers from each government - in different

[affairs.ec.europa.eu/system/files_en?file=2020-11/summary_of_consultations_in_view_of_the_action_plan_on_integration_and_inclusion.pdf](https://affairs.ec.europa.eu/system/files/en?file=2020-11/summary_of_consultations_in_view_of_the_action_plan_on_integration_and_inclusion.pdf)
[Consulted in 06/2022]

³⁶ European Commission (2022) 'EXPERT GROUP ON THE VIEWS OF MIGRANTS IN THE FIELD OF MIGRATION, ASYLUM AND INTEGRATION (E03734)', Available at: <https://ec.europa.eu/transparency/expert-groups-register/screen/expert-groups/consult?do=groupDetail.groupDetail&groupID=3734> [Accessed in 06/2022]

³⁷ European Union (2022) 'Types of institutions and bodies', Available at: https://european-union.europa.eu/institutions-law-budget/institutions-and-bodies/types-institutions-and-bodies_en [Consulted on 25/11/2022]

configurations depending on the topic to be discussed - meet to adopt laws and coordinate policies.

- the **European Parliament** (EP) represents and is directly elected by the EU citizens; it approves the EU budget, and along with the Council of the European Union, it takes decisions on European laws.
- the **European Court of Justice** (ECJ) reviews the legality of the acts of the EU institutions, ensures that EU countries comply with their obligations under the Treaties, and interprets the Treaties and EU law at the request of national courts.
- the **European Central Bank** (ECB) and the European System of Central Banks are responsible for the monetary and exchange rate policy in the Eurozone, keep prices stable in the euro area, and support EU economic policies.
- the **European Court of Auditors** (ECA) acts as the independent guardian of the financial interests of EU citizens, promoting accountability and transparency by checking on the correct expenditure of EU funds.

Since the Lisbon Treaty in 2009, the co-decision procedure was renamed the ordinary legislative procedure and - applying to around 85 policy areas - it became the main decision-making procedure used to adopt EU legislation.³⁸ According to it, the EC submits a proposal to the Council and the EP, who are the co-legislators and who are called to agree on a final version of the text. If a legislative proposal is rejected at any stage of the procedure, or a compromise is not reached by the co-legislators, the proposal is not adopted and the procedure comes to an end.

In addition to the institutions mentioned above, there are other bodies which help the EU to fulfil its tasks by playing specialised roles. Some advise the institutions (the **European Economic and Social Committee**, the **European Committee of the Regions**), others ensure that the institutions comply with EU rules and procedures (the **European Ombudsman**, the **European Data Protection Supervisor**). The **European External Action Service** supports the EU on foreign affairs matters.³⁹ Finally, important sectors are regulated by independent agencies (by 2019, there were more than 40 agencies and independent authorities), which may differ from executive to regulatory, but all have financial and management autonomy, specific missions, and independent executive bodies.⁴⁰

In some policy areas, such as single market policies and competition policies, the EU works as a federation in a supranational logic: the integration of the European Union proceeds through law and the power is shared among the EC, the EP, the Council, the

³⁸ European Council (2022) 'The ordinary legislative procedure', Available at: <https://www.consilium.europa.eu/en/council-eu/decision-making/ordinary-legislative-procedure/>. [Consulted on 25/11/22]

³⁹ European Union (2022) 'Types of institutions and bodies', Available at: https://european-union.europa.eu/institutions-law-budget/institutions-and-bodies/types-institutions-and-bodies_en [Consulted on 25/11/2022]

⁴⁰ *Ibid.*

European Council.⁴¹ Here, the executive power is represented by the European Commission and the European Council. In other policy areas, such as foreign and security policies and the economic policy of the Economic and Monetary Union (EMU), the EU works as an International Organisation, in an intergovernmental logic. Indeed, in domains like foreign policy and defence policy, the ordinary legislative procedure is not used, the European Parliament has no formal role, only the Council decides under unanimity, and the Commission cannot initiate decision-making but only execute tasks delegated by the Council. Here, the executive power is represented by the European Council and the Council.⁴² In the field of migration and asylum, the ordinary legislative procedure applies, which means that the EC submits a proposal to the Council and the European Parliament, who are the co-legislators and who are called to agree on a final version of the text.

More specifically, the domain of migration is regulated by a number of treaties, agendas, directives, with the support of agencies and funding. The European Commission **Directorate-General for Migration and Home Affairs (DG HOME) is in charge of migration and home affairs**, under the leadership of Commissioner Ylva Johansson since 2019.⁴³ The **Justice and Home Affairs Council (JHA)** composed of the justice and home affairs ministers of the 27 Member States develop cooperation and common policies on migration and asylum matters.⁴⁴ The European Parliament (particularly the **Committee on Civil Liberties, Justice and Home Affairs - LIBE**) has powers of 'co-decision' over migration policy, meaning it votes on legislation along with the Council.⁴⁵

The governance of migration and diversity at EU level differs when we speak of intra-European migrants or EU nationals, extra-European migrants or Third Country Nationals (TCNs), and migrants seeking international protection.

EU nationals: The free circulation of EU nationals across Member States is provided by the **Schengen** intergovernmental agreement (1985), which was integrated into EU Law with the 1997 Treaty of Amsterdam. The EU has also encouraged the circulation of students with the 1987 Erasmus programme, and **2014 Erasmus +**.⁴⁶

Third Country Nationals: With the 1992 Maastricht Treaty, migration policy-making was an intergovernmental 'pillar'. But it is the 2009 Lisbon Treaty (articles 77–80) that set out the

⁴¹ Fabbrini, S. (2020) 'Institutions and Decision-Making in the EU', *Governance and Politics in the Post-Crisis European Union*, 54-73. Available at: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/346988185_Institutions_and_Decision-Making_in_the_EU [Accessed on 25/11/2022]

⁴² *Ibid.*

⁴³ European Commission (2022) 'Migration and Home Affairs', Available at: https://ec.europa.eu/info/departments/migration-and-home-affairs_en [Consulted on 25/11/2022]

⁴⁴ European Council (2022) 'Justice and Home Affairs Council configuration (JHA)', Available at: <https://www.consilium.europa.eu/en/council-eu/configurations/jha/> [Consulted on 25/11/2022]

⁴⁵ Committees European Parliament (2022) 'Committee on Civil Liberties, Justice and Home Affairs', Available at: <https://www.europarl.europa.eu/committees/en/libe/home/highlights> [Consulted on 25/11/2022].

⁴⁶ European Parliament Fact Sheets on the European Union (2022) 'Free movement of persons', Available at: <https://www.europarl.europa.eu/factsheets/en/sheet/147/free-movement-of-persons> [Accessed on 30/11/2022].

EU's competences on borders, asylum, and immigration.⁴⁷ The EU committed to 'the principle of solidarity and fair sharing of responsibility' as a governing principle for migration policy. Migration was brought entirely under the community method, empowering the European Parliament and European Court of Justice. Under the qualifying majority vote procedure (55% Member States, 65% of EU population), single Member States cannot veto legislation. An important remark: **The EU and its Member States share the competence in the area of migration.**⁴⁸ **The EU provides common procedures and rights - including the 2011 Single Permit Directive - whereas the national level is still the relevant sovereign entity for the management of entries.** The EU level is also relevant for refusing entries: the EU agency **European Border and Coast Guard Agency**, also known as **Frontex** (2004, repealed by Regulation (EU) 2016/1624) manages the external borders of Europe. The EU also issued **directives on curbing irregular migration (2008)** and **facilitating return (2009).**⁴⁹

International protection: Asylum seekers and refugees are also a shared competence of the EU and Member States. It was first addressed at Tampere with the adoption of the Common European Asylum System (CEAS) (1999). But the latest Treaty of Lisbon (2009) establishes a uniform status of asylum which includes: a uniform status of subsidiary protection, a common system of temporary protection, common procedures for the granting and withdrawing of uniform asylum or subsidiary protection status, criteria and mechanisms for determining which Member State is responsible for considering an application - that is, the system coupling the Dublin Regulation and EURODAC Regulation (Europe-wide fingerprinting database) with aims to "determine rapidly the Member State responsible for an asylum claim" (1990, 2003, 2013, 2017), standards concerning reception conditions, and partnership and cooperation with third countries. After several reforms and heating negotiations following 2015, **the CEAS was reformed in 2020.** The **European Union Agency for Asylum** contributes to improving the functioning and implementation of the Common European Asylum System.

Within the framework of MILE project, we will focus on EU nationals "with migrant background" (see Action Plan), TCNs and refugees (or people awaiting international protection).

2.2. Migration and integration policy

⁴⁷ Hampshire, J. (2016). European migration governance since the Lisbon treaty: introduction to the special issue. *Journal of Ethnic and Migration Studies*, 42(4), 537-553.

⁴⁸ James Hampshire (2016) Speaking with one voice? The European Union's global approach to migration and mobility and the limits of international migration cooperation, *Journal of Ethnic and Migration Studies*, 42:4, 571-586.

⁴⁹ European Commission (2022). 'Legal migration and integration', Available at: https://home-affairs.ec.europa.eu/policies/migration-and-asylum/legal-migration-and-integration_en [Accessed on 7/12/22]

In the EU context, migration policies govern entries and exits in and out the European space. Integration has been defined as “a dynamic, two-way process of mutual accommodation by all immigrants and residents of EU Member States”.⁵⁰ This definition is also the most commonly accepted in the scholarship.⁵¹ Yet, recently, ‘integration’ is often replaced and/or complemented with the concept of ‘inclusion’, a more proactive response to the diversity and complexity of migrants’ experiences, which aims at equity.⁵²

*Migration policy*⁵³: The EU shares competence with Member States in this field. “The EU aims to set up a balanced approach to managing regular immigration and combating irregular immigration. Proper management of migration flows entails ensuring fair treatment of third-country nationals residing legally in Member States, enhancing measures to combat irregular immigration, including trafficking and smuggling, and promoting closer cooperation with non-member countries in all fields”.⁵⁴ The EU migration policy is presently under revision. In September 2020, the Commission proposed the **New Pact on Asylum and Migration** aimed at providing a comprehensive common European framework for migration and asylum management. It is composed of various legislative proposals in the hands of the EP LIBE Committee, DG HOME and the Council, including a new Asylum and Migration Management Regulation, a new Screening Regulation, a new Crisis and Force Majeure Regulation, an amended proposal revising the Asylum Procedures Regulation, an amended proposal revising the EUODAC Regulation, and a regulation establishing the EU Asylum Agency.

At the end of 2022, these proposals are awaiting to be discussed in the Council, which is currently working on the EUODAC Regulation and the Screening Regulation. The main focus is on border control and securitization: this New Pact is still linked to a securitarian approach to migration which aims at slowing down the phenomenon, does not invest in policies of welcoming and inclusion and is ambiguous on the topic of the internal free movement of people (Interview 5). Moreover, it is very precise in the definition of return policies, but not on mandatory cooperation among countries (interview 5). In September 2022, a new agreement has been reached amongst the European Parliament President Roberta Metsola, Chair of the Civil Liberties Committee Juan Fernando López Aguilar, Asylum Contact Group Chair Elena Yoncheva, and the Permanent Representatives of Czechia, Sweden, Spain, Belgium and France regarding the conduct of negotiations

⁵⁰ European Commission (n/a) ‘Integration’, Available at: https://home-affairs.ec.europa.eu/pages/glossary/integration_en [Accessed on 16/09/2022]

⁵¹ Penninx, R., & Garcés-Mascreñas, B. (2016) The concept of integration as an analytical tool and as a policy concept. In: *Integration processes and policies in Europe* (pp. 11-29). Springer, Cham.

⁵² Friends of Europe (2019) ‘Discussion Paper. Europe’s migration challenge: from integration to inclusion’, Available at: <https://www.friendsofeurope.org/insights/europes-migration-challenge-from-integration-to-inclusion/> [Accessed on 25/11/2022]

⁵³ European Parliament (2022) ‘Immigration Policy’, Available at: <https://www.europarl.europa.eu/factsheets/en/sheet/152/immigration-policy> [Accessed in 06/2022]

⁵⁴ *Ibid.*

between the co-legislators with a view to reforming EU migration and Asylum rules (the EU New Pact) by February 2024 and generally before the end of the current legislature.⁵⁵

*Integration policy*⁵⁶: Although the responsibility for integration policies lies primarily with Member States, the EU has established some measures to support national as well as regional and local authorities, and civil society, in their efforts to promote integration and inclusion. In 2004, in the attempt of developing a common migration policy, the Justice and Home Affairs Council agreed on common basic principles for immigrant integration policy in the EU, which were then reaffirmed in 2014.⁵⁷ In 2011, the Commission proposed a European agenda for the integration of TCNs, stressing the importance of the local action. Indeed, since the 1980s, the EU has slowly recognised the role of cities as relevant European actors, including in the field of integration policies.

- The European Committee of the Regions (established in 1994), for instance, has launched in 2019 the **Cities and Regions for Integration Initiative** (CRII) to promote exchanges between local and regional authorities working on integration.
- In a similar logic, the Urban Agenda for the EU⁵⁸ has fostered the “**Urban Agenda for the EU Partnership on Inclusion of Migrants and Refugees**” (2016-2019)⁵⁹ which has led to the accomplishment of two of the goals of its 2017 Action plan: the establishment of the **European Migrant Advisory Board** as well as of the **Urban Academy for Integration**. The Urban Agenda for the EU is included in the European Commission **Futurium** platform⁶⁰ - a mechanism of the EU for the participation of citizens in policy-related forums. One group is focused on the Inclusion of Migrants and Refugees.

⁵⁵ European Parliament News (2022) ‘Migration and Asylum: Roadmap on way forward agreed between the European Parliament and rotating Presidencies’, Available at: <https://www.europarl.europa.eu/news/en/press-room/20220905IPR39714/migration-and-asylum-roadmap-on-way-forward-agreed> [Accessed in 09/2022]

⁵⁶ European Commission (2022) ‘European Integration Network’, Available at: https://ec.europa.eu/migrant-integration/eu-grid/european-integration-network_en [Accessed in 06/2022].

⁵⁷ Council of the European Union (2004) Press release, Available at: https://ec.europa.eu/migrant-integration/library-document/common-basic-principles-immigrant-integration-policy-eu_en [Accessed on 15/10/2022].

⁵⁸ The Urban Agenda for the EU was launched in 2016 and is an integrated and coordinated approach to deal with the urban dimension of the EU and national policies and legislation. It is a new multi-level working method which promotes cooperation between Member States, cities, the European Commission, and other stakeholders, with the aim of improving the quality of life, innovation and growth in urban areas, and identifying and tackling social challenges. Up until now, it has established 14 partnerships of which one is dedicated to the inclusion of migrants and refugees, bringing together cities, EU countries, the European Commission and civil society organisations to develop common actions to promote integration. More information is available at: <https://www.inclusionpartnership.com>.

⁵⁹ Stürner-Siovit, J., & Heimann, C. (2022) ‘The EU Urban Partnership on Inclusion: Institutionalizing Local–Supranational Integration Governance’, *International Migration Review*, First published online June 22, 2022.

⁶⁰ European Commission (2021) ‘Inclusion of Migrants and Refugees’, Available at: <https://futurium.ec.europa.eu/en/urban-agenda/inclusion-migrants-and-refugees> [Accessed on 08/08/2022]

The project URBAN, which then became **URBACT** where city actors share best practices is another case in point.

In 2016, this agenda was complemented by an action plan on the integration of TCNs, in support of the different actors and the different tiers of government involved in the integration effort.⁶¹ Subsequently, **the new EU Action Plan on Integration and Inclusion (2021-2027)** was launched **by the European Commission**, clarifying that national governments are primarily responsible for the design of integration and social policies (education, employment, housing, healthcare), whereas the EU plays a fundamental role in supporting them and other stakeholders through funding, developing practical tools, coordinating actions and establishing relevant partnerships.

The Action Plan proposes concrete actions, gives guidance and delineates funding for initiatives meant to bring inclusion for all. In the context of the “local turn”⁶², cities are increasingly seen as the level where integration occurs and where its concrete challenges need to be faced. As the European Website on Integration makes clear, the EU’s actions are inspired by a ‘multi-stakeholder’ approach to integration, one which involves not only national authorities but also local and regional authorities, who implement policies on the ground and provide basic, vital services.⁶³ The growing synergy between EU urban policies and EU integration policies is further reflected in the 2016-2019 Inclusion Partnership of the Urban Agenda of the EU, which focuses on migrants and refugees’ integration.⁶⁴

With the new Action Plan, EU nationals with a migrant background are included in the strategy, along with the already present TCNs. In addition, greater importance is given to enhancing migrant participation, for example through the recent creation of an Expert Group on the views of migrants within the European Commission. Moreover, the new Action Plan brings additional focus on building more partnerships with various integration stakeholders and on long-term integration, also through funding.⁶⁵ It is worth

⁶¹ European Parliamentary Research Service (2021) ‘Labour market integration of asylum-seekers and refugees’, June 2021, Available at: [https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/BRIE/2021/690651/EPRS_BRI\(2021\)690651_EN.pdf](https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/BRIE/2021/690651/EPRS_BRI(2021)690651_EN.pdf) [Accessed on 05/10/2022]

⁶² See Scholten, P., & Penninx, R. (2016) ‘The multilevel governance of migration and integration’, In: *Integration processes and policies in Europe* (pp. 91-108). Springer, Cham; and Zapata-Barrero, R., Caponio, T., & Scholten, P. (2017) ‘Theorizing the ‘local turn’ in a multi-level governance framework of analysis: A case study in immigrant policies’, *International Review of Administrative Sciences*, 83(2), p. 241-246.

⁶³ European Commission (2022) ‘EU strategy - why integration matters for the EU’, Available at: https://ec.europa.eu/migrant-integration/eu-grid/eu-strategy_en [Accessed in 06/2022]

⁶⁴ European Commission (2022) ‘Inclusion of Migrants and Refugees. Part of Urban Agenda for the EU’, Available at: <https://futurium.ec.europa.eu/en/urban-agenda/inclusion-migrants-and-refugees> [Accessed on 25/11/2022]

⁶⁵ Italian Ministry of Work and Social Policies (2020) ‘EU Action Plan on Integration and Inclusion (2021-2027)’, Available at: <https://integrazionemigranti.gov.it/en-gb/Dettaglio-approfondimento/id/1/EU-Action-Plan-on-Integration-and-Inclusion-2021-2027> [Accessed in 08/2022]

noting that the EU is in the midst of a change of narrative. As advocated by researchers,⁶⁶ the new shared best practices are related to a view of integration that is the responsibility of society as a whole: “Developing welcoming, diverse and inclusive societies is a process that needs the engagement of both migrants and the receiving society”.⁶⁷

Regarding integration policy and the New Action Plan, it is worth observing that other EU institutions’ work on integration dates back some time. The **Council’s** last actions date back to December 2016, when it adopted conclusions on the integration of TCNs legally residing in the EU, inviting Member States to exchange best practices, improve monitoring and assessment, address the recognition of qualifications and skills of TCNs.⁶⁸ It has not adopted conclusions on the Commission’s 2020 Action Plan yet. The **Parliament**, in its resolution of 20 May 2021, noted that the divergent implementation of the existing directives by the Member States can hinder integration and that enhanced intra-EU mobility would allow TCNs already in the EU to improve their integration prospects.⁶⁹ The **Committee of the Regions** had given its opinion⁷⁰ to the 2016 Action plan, but not for the 2020 one yet.

Finally, it is important to highlight that in April 2022, the Commission - as part of its legal migration package - launched the EU talent pool project, aimed at attracting TCNs to the EU labour market by matching the labour offer and demand.⁷¹

Specific funds: A major shift has occurred in the last multiannual framework programme 2021-2027 regarding the funds allocated to integration of TCNs in the EU. The introduction of a differentiation between short-term and long-term integration has been made, according to the different needs that Member States face in the process. Thanks to this shift, local and regional governments started to be mentioned as direct beneficiaries of some of the funds.⁷² Funds related to migration and integration policies

⁶⁶ Penninx, R., & Garcés-Mascreñas, B. (2016) ‘The concept of integration as an analytical tool and as a policy concept’, In: *Integration processes and policies in Europe* (pp. 11-29). Springer, Cham.

⁶⁷ European Commission (2020) ‘Action plan on Integration and Inclusion 2021-2027’, Available at: https://home-affairs.ec.europa.eu/system/files_en?file=2020-11/action_plan_on_integration_and_inclusion_2021-2027.pdf , p. 20.

⁶⁸ Council of Europe (2016) ‘Conclusions of the Council and the Representatives of the Governments of the Member States on the integration of third-country nationals legally residing in the EU - Council conclusions (9 December 2016)’, Available at: <https://data.consilium.europa.eu/doc/document/ST-15312-2016-INIT/en/pdf> [Accessed in 06/2022]

⁶⁹ European Parliament (2022) ‘Action Plan on Integration and Inclusion in: Promoting our European Way of Life’, Available at: <https://www.europarl.europa.eu/legislative-train/theme-promoting-our-european-way-of-life/file-action-plan-on-integration-and-inclusion> [Accessed in 08/2022]

⁷⁰ European Committee of the Regions (2016) ‘Action plan on the integration of third country nationals’, Available at: <https://cor.europa.eu/en/our-work/Documents/Integration-initiative/cor-2016-04438-00-00-ac-tra-en.pdf> [Accessed in 08/2022]

⁷¹ European Parliamentary Research Service (June 2021) ‘Labour market integration of asylum-seekers and refugees’, Available at: [https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/BRIE/2021/690651/EPRS_BRI\(2021\)690651_EN.pdf](https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/BRIE/2021/690651/EPRS_BRI(2021)690651_EN.pdf) [Accessed on 05/10/2022]

⁷² Eurocities (n/a) ‘Overview of the EU funding programmes 2021-2027’, Available at: https://nws.eurocities.eu/MediaShell/media/Funding_Overview_2021-2027_-_Eurocities.pdf [Accessed in 09/2022].

are the Asylum, Migration and Integration fund (AMIF) to support early integration, European Social Fund Plus (ESF+),⁷³ European Regional Development Fund (ERDF), Erasmus+, and the European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development (EAFRD) to support medium and long-term integration.⁷⁴

2.3 Diversity and equality policy

2.3.1 Commitment to equality, diversity and inclusion

Equality and diversity are among the main priorities of the EU, who has adopted a proactive approach with targeted action plans to fight discrimination and push for more equal societies. In 2019, Helena Dalli - who will hold her post until 2024 - was appointed as EU Commissioner for equality: her main task is strengthening the EU's commitment to inclusion and equality in all of its senses. In this context, for instance, the EC has launched in 2022 the European Capitals of Inclusion and Diversity Award, aimed at complementing the annual EU Diversity Month.⁷⁵ The EU has also promoted various Action Plans to tackle discrimination and initiatives to promote gender equality and equal pay rules, Roma integration, LGBTI equality, among others.⁷⁶

Focusing on migration and integration, since the 1980s on and the promulgation of the Schengen treaty, Europe has promoted the free circulation of persons. The EU communicates that its Member States have an ageing population and a need to attract skilled persons. Migrant integration is viewed as a vital component of the competitiveness of the EU economy.⁷⁷ The European website on integration has communicated that migrants are disproportionately affected by unfavourable outcomes in terms of education, employment and access to basic services such as healthcare and decent housing.⁷⁸ Yet, they are "key to the well-being, prosperity and cohesion of European societies". As integration is not a competence of the EU, its role in integration matters is perceived primarily as a provider of incentives, support, and coordination of actions for EU members. Since the late 1990s, long-term integration of migrants has been included

⁷³ Since 2021, it includes the former European Social Fund. See the page of the EU Programme for Employment and Social Innovation (EaSI), Available at: <https://ec.europa.eu/social/main.jsp?catId=1081>.

⁷⁴ European Commission (2022) 'Inclusion of migrants and refugees in cities', Available at: https://ec.europa.eu/info/eu-regional-and-urban-development/topics/cities-and-urban-development/priority-themes-eu-cities/inclusion-migrants-and-refugees-cities_en [Accessed on 25/11/2022]

⁷⁵ European Capitals of Inclusion and Diversity Award (2022) [consulted on 30/11/2022]

⁷⁶ European Commission (2022) 'Combating discrimination', Available at: https://ec.europa.eu/info/policies/justice-and-fundamental-rights/combating-discrimination_en [Consulted on 30/11/2022]

⁷⁷ European Commission (2022) 'EU strategy - why integration matters for the EU', Available at: https://ec.europa.eu/migrant-integration/eu-grid/eu-strategy_en [Accessed in 06/2022]

⁷⁸ European Commission (2022) 'EU strategy - why integration matters for the EU', Available at: https://ec.europa.eu/migrant-integration/eu-grid/eu-strategy_en [Accessed in 06/2022]; European Commission (2020) 'Action plan on Integration and Inclusion 2021-2027', Available at: https://home-affairs.ec.europa.eu/system/files_en?file=2020-11/action_plan_on_integration_and_inclusion_2021-2027.pdf [Accessed in 06/2022]

in all EU agendas regarding migration and integration. The economic dimension of integration is the most prominent dimension. In that sense, scholars have highlighted that the EU sees diversity as a factor of economic development.⁷⁹

Although EU policy documents tend to portray migrants as potential economic actors, and therefore reduced to their economic contribution, some EU-funded projects have taken a broader approach and consider life stories or cultural heritage beyond the economic role of migrants. This is the case of the AMIF-funded “Specially Unknown”.⁸⁰ We can also mention the MAX project, with a specific Work Package focused on the representation of migrants in the media and a training for journalists.⁸¹

2.3.2 Strategy for promoting diversity and equal opportunities

The EC’s commitment to equality and inclusion is strengthened through various EU strategies aimed at tackling discrimination and promoting inclusion, such as the Gender Equality Strategy (2020-2025),⁸² LGBTIQ Equality Strategy 2020-2025,⁸³ EU Anti-Racism Action Plan 2020-2025,⁸⁴ and Roma Strategic framework on equality, inclusion and participation 2020-2030.⁸⁵ With a specific focus on migration and integration, we can add the New EU Action Plan on Integration and Inclusion 2021-2027 where diversity and equal opportunities are key themes.

With a narrower focus on the New Action Plan on Integration and Inclusion, the main sectoral policy areas it focuses on (in its fourth paragraph) are: Education and training, Employment and skills, Health, and Housing. The plan lists, as key stakeholders, local governments, civil society organisations, educational institutions, employers and socio-economic partners, social economy organisations, churches, religious and other philosophical communities, youth and students’ organisations, diaspora organisations, and migrants themselves.⁸⁶

⁷⁹ Soysal, Y. N. (2012) ‘Citizenship, immigration, and the European social project: rights and obligations of individuality’, *The British Journal of Sociology* 63(1), 1-21.

⁸⁰ Specially Unknown (n/a) ‘About the project’, Available at: <https://speciallyunknown.eu/about-the-project/> [Accessed in 08/2022]

⁸¹ Max Project on Maximising Migrants’ Contribution to Society. Information available at: <https://maxamif.eu/> [Accessed in 08/2022]

⁸² European Commission (2022) ‘Gender Equality Strategy’, Available at: https://ec.europa.eu/info/policies/justice-and-fundamental-rights/gender-equality/gender-equality-strategy_en#gender-equality-strategy-2020-2025 [Accessed on 30/11/2022]

⁸³ European Commission (2022) ‘LGBTIQ Equality Strategy 2020-2025’, Available at: https://ec.europa.eu/info/policies/justice-and-fundamental-rights/combating-discrimination/lesbian-gay-bi-trans-and-intersex-equality/lgbtiq-equality-strategy-2020-2025_en [Accessed on 25/11/2022]

⁸⁴ European Commission (2022) ‘EU Anti-racism Action Plan 2020-2025’, Available at: https://ec.europa.eu/info/policies/justice-and-fundamental-rights/combating-discrimination/racism-and-xenophobia/eu-anti-racism-action-plan-2020-2025_en [Accessed on 25/11/2022]

⁸⁵ European Commission (2020) ‘The new EU Roma strategic framework for equality, inclusion and participation’, Available at: https://ec.europa.eu/info/publications/new-eu-roma-strategic-framework-equality-inclusion-and-participation-full-package_en [Accessed on 25/11/2022]

⁸⁶ European Commission (2020) ‘Action plan on Integration and Inclusion 2021-2027’, Available at: https://home-affairs.ec.europa.eu/system/files_en?file=2020-11/action_plan_on_integration_and_inclusion_2021-2027.pdf, p7.

European integration policies are backed up by consequent funding; several funds are available, such as: Asylum, Migration and Integration fund (AMIF) to support early integration (set up by DG HOME, and instrumental to the European integration policies, the budget has tripled from EUR 3.137 billion for 2014-2020, to EUR 9.9 billion for 2021-2027); the European Social Fund Plus (ESF+); the European Regional Development Fund (ERDF); Erasmus+: the European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development (EAFRD) to support for medium and long-term integration. After the invasion of Ukraine by Russia, the European Commission decided for a Cohesion's Action for Refugees in Europe (CARE) of over 370 billion Euros of cohesion funds, then fostered by the FAST-CARE (see 3.2, BOX 3). Also, the Citizens, Equality, Rights and Values program (CERV) – aimed at supporting and further developing democratic, equal and inclusive societies – covers topics such as intersectionality and vulnerable groups like migrant women or children.

2.3.3 Consideration of intersectionality

At the EC level, several 'directorates' or departments have within their remit a commitment to tackle different 'axes of inequality', including DG JUST (Directorate-General for Justice and Consumers), responsible for the respect of human rights, gender equality and initiatives aimed at combatting discrimination (see 2.3.2); DG EMPL (Employment Social Affairs and Inclusion), which works to address the multidimensional phenomenon of inequality and its outcomes in terms of income, education or health; for our matter here, DG HOME (Migration and Home Affairs), which is responsible for migration policy and it is therefore the main directorate dedicated to dealing with migration-related inequalities.

Moreover, the Commission has developed a Multidimensional Inequality Monitoring Framework for the EU, aimed at contributing to the measurement, monitoring and analysis of a wide range of different aspects of inequality. in order to gather extensive knowledge on inequalities across various life domains. It is a comprehensive dashboard of country level inequality indicators, referring to ten life domains: knowledge and skills, health, material living conditions, natural and environmental conditions, working life, cultural life and recreation, political participation and voice, social and family life, bodily integrity and safety, and overall life experience.⁸⁷

In general, the EU institutions appear to be moving towards an intersectional approach in seeking to tackle multiple 'axes of inequality' simultaneously. The various action plans - the Gender Equality Strategy 2020-2025, the EU anti-racism action plan 2020-2025, the EU Roma Strategic Framework for equality, inclusion and participation, the LGBTIQ Equality Strategy and the forthcoming Strategy on the rights of persons with disabilities - do adopt an intersectional approach. For instance, the immigrant status is always mentioned as an additional ground for discrimination.

⁸⁷ European Commission (2022) 'EU Multidimensional Inequality Monitoring Framework', Available at: <https://composite-indicators.jrc.ec.europa.eu/multidimensional-inequality> [Accessed on 25/11/2022]

Looking more specifically at the new Action Plan on Integration and Inclusion, as advertised by the EC in a press release⁸⁸, it aims at “mainstreaming gender and including women”, highlighting particular challenges faced by migrant women in areas of employment and access to health services. The plan itself details that “this action plan will take into account the combination of personal characteristics, such as gender, racial or ethnic origin, religion or belief, sexual orientation and disability that can represent specific challenges for migrants. It will build on and complement” the above-mentioned strategies and action plans (2020, p. 6).

In sum, in recent years, the EC has embraced more explicitly the concept of intersectionality, started building a more comprehensive policy framework applying this cross-cutting concept across various areas and collaborating with actors from the civil society (e.g. European Network Against Racism, ENAR). In this context, in July 2022, the EP adopted a resolution on intersectional discrimination in the EU and the socio-economic situation of women of African, Middle-Eastern, Latin-American and Asian descent, which represents the first EU document specifically focused on the topic of intersectionality.⁸⁹

DG HOME is the main directorate dedicated to dealing with migration-related inequalities. Yet the EU has other mechanisms. For instance, the European Commission has adopted the EU anti-racism action plan 2020-2025 to tackle racism and to achieve a ‘Union of Equality’. It works closely with civil society, including the large European Network Against Racism (ENAR).

⁸⁸ European Commission (2020) ‘The EC reveals its new EU Action Plan on Integration and Inclusion (2021-2027)’, Available at: https://ec.europa.eu/migrant-integration/news/ec-reveals-its-new-eu-action-plan-integration-and-inclusion-2021-2027_en [Accessed in 06/2022]

⁸⁹ European Parliament (2022) ‘Intersectional discrimination in the European Union: the socio-economic situation of women of African, Middle-Eastern, Latin-American and Asian descent’, Available at: [https://oeil.secure.europarl.europa.eu/oeil/popups/ficheprocedure.do?reference=2021/2243\(INI\)&l=en](https://oeil.secure.europarl.europa.eu/oeil/popups/ficheprocedure.do?reference=2021/2243(INI)&l=en) [Accessed on 06/2022].

3 THE EVOLUTION OF INCLUSIVITY OF MIGRANTS IN POLICY MAKING

3.1 Migrant inclusion in EU policy making

The inclusivity of migrants in EU policy making dates back from the 1992 Treaty of Maastrich: EU nationals have the right to vote for the European Parliament, regardless of their residence country. Member States have also opened local elections to EU nationals residing in another EU Member State. A few years later, at the Tampere Conference of 1999, the Common European Asylum System (CEAS) was established and MS called for more consideration of the positive effects of migrant flows on the economic development of the sending countries, and on the economies and demography of the countries of arrival.⁹⁰

Tampere and the CEAS were a first step towards a new approach of migrants' long-term integration. But it seems that the question of integration of third-country nationals (TCNs) grew bigger after 09/11, a global event which had an important effect on the migration-security nexus worldwide.⁹¹ In fact, the Justice and Home Affairs (JHA) Council requested in 2002 to establish National Contact Points on integration (NCPs). The European Council of June 2003 confirmed that mandate and invited the Commission to present Annual Reports on Migration and Integration.⁹² In November 2004, the first edition of a Handbook on Integration for policy-makers and practitioners was published. The **Hague Programme** was adopted by the European Council in November 2004 and underlined the need for greater coordination of national integration policies and EU initiatives in this field.

EU enlargements that we highlight in the timeline of progress on migrant inclusion in policy making (table 1) have been key moments in the change of the legal framework, and the diversification of the Parliament, the weight of voters, and more importantly for our matter, because groups of migrants that were previously outside of the EU (and hence, TCNs) became EU nationals. In 2004 in particular, as Malta, Cyprus, Estonia, Lithuania, Latvia, Poland, Czech Republic, Slovakia, Slovenia, and Hungary entered the EU, the effects were multiple, including new dynamics of inclusion and exclusion of EU movers and TCNs, new patterns of circulatory migration, and changes in the labour market.⁹³

In **2005, A Common Agenda for Integration Framework for the Integration of Third-Country Nationals in the European Union**⁹⁴ was adopted. Among the various items on

⁹⁰ European Parliament (1999) 'TAMPERE EUROPEAN COUNCIL 15 AND 16 OCTOBER 1999 - PRESIDENCY CONCLUSIONS', Available at: https://www.europarl.europa.eu/summits/tam_en.htm [Accessed in 08/2022]

⁹¹ Faist, T. (2006) 'The migration-security nexus: International migration and security before and after 9/11', In: *Migration, citizenship, ethnos* (pp. 103-119). Palgrave Macmillan, New York.

⁹² Commission of the European Communities (2005) 'A Common Agenda for Integration Framework for the Integration of Third-Country Nationals in the European Union', Available at: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=COM:2005:0389:FIN:en:PDF> [Accessed in 08/2022].

⁹³ Adrian Favell & Randall Hansen (2002) 'Markets against politics: Migration, EU enlargement and the idea of Europe', *Journal of Ethnic and Migration Studies* 28(4): 581-601.

⁹⁴ *Ibid.*

the agenda is point (9) which states that 'The participation of immigrants in the democratic process and in the formulation of integration policies and measures, especially at the local level, supports their integration'. To that end, one of the 5 objectives at the EU level is "Fostering the creation of a platform of migrants' organisations and organisations representing migrants' interests at EU level". The same year, country coordinators of all Member States included the new **European Integration Network** (2005) in order to get updated information on the EU agenda, and share best practices.

The **European Integration Network**⁹⁵ brings together representatives of national public authorities and mainly from the ministries responsible for migrant integration. The 32 members and/or the 28 alternate members meet every six months in order for the EC to inform them on current developments, initiatives, policies, and fundings in the field of integration (interview 2). Members also share best practices in their national contexts. The Network still functions today. The Hague Programme called explicitly for the development of a widely accessible Internet website. The European Integration Network was created in parallel to another initiative: the **European Website on Integration (EWSI)**.⁹⁶ To finance this new agenda, between 2007-2013, the Commission proposed new solidarity instruments, among them the **European Fund for the Integration of third-country nationals**, which preceded the Asylum, Migration and Integration Fund that we know today. Along that period, in **2009** the **Lisbon treaty entered into force**, and an European Parliament election took place.

The **first ever Eurobarometer on Migrant Integration was conducted in March and April 2011**.⁹⁷ The Eurobarometer enables the gathering of the opinion of (a representative sample of around a 1000) Europeans on migration and integration issues. This wide consultation with EU residents continues to exist through the Eurobarometer. The will of the EU to consult its residents on integration matters is sustained as the survey from 2021 included a question on the Integration of Immigrants in the European Union.⁹⁸

In 2015, the so-called "refugee crisis", which reached a peak in 2015, triggered a governance crisis in the EU. The "principle of solidarity" established in Maastricht, and the Dublin system were put in question. Several expert groups on migration-related matters have been formed to deal with specific issues such as economic migration or unaccompanied minors and to be consulted, involving individuals and civil society organisations. Chronologically, these expert groups are: the **Expert group on economic**

⁹⁵ European Commission (n/a), 'European Integration Network', Available at: https://ec.europa.eu/migrant-integration/eu-grid/european-integration-network_en [Accessed in 06/2022].

⁹⁶ Access here: https://ec.europa.eu/migrant-integration/home_en

⁹⁷ European Commission (2011) 'Eurobarometer on Migrant Integration', Available at: https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/en/MEMO_11_529 [Accessed in 06/2022]

⁹⁸ European Commission (2022) 'Integration of Immigrants in the European Union', Available at: <https://europa.eu/eurobarometer/surveys/detail/2276> [Accessed in 06/2022]

migration⁹⁹ (2015) which includes representatives of academic centres, trade unions, chambers of commerce, as well as individuals asked to provide feedback on EU policy proposals regarding labour migration; the **Commission Expert Group on the Protection of Children in Migration**¹⁰⁰ (2017) created while increased numbers of children reached Europe alone; and **the European Migrant Advisory Board**¹⁰¹, a self-made group of TCNs established following the Urban Agenda for the EU Partnership on Inclusion of Migrants and Refugees (2016-2019) and the acknowledgment that current asylum policies were failing. Indeed, when interviewed, a board's member directly linked the 2015 EU governance crisis with the partnership and the creation of the board (interview 1). In 2018, the Board conducted a large public consultation called "Ask the People"¹⁰².

Following the so-called refugee crisis is another important event for the EU and migration matters: the 2016 vote in favour of Brexit. Indeed, with the UK leaving the union, it is not only trade and finance that are at stake, but also, the expression of an increased resentment of a (short majority of British voters towards immigration, both of free movers and TCNs).¹⁰³

The onset of Covid 19 in 2020, and its disproportionate effect on migrants, is another critical event. The 2021-2027 Action Plan was developed in this period, with a higher fund (AMIF tripled). It is worth noting that new treaties and common policies are significant milestones. The 2021-2027 Action Plan, as much as the Lisbon treaty before, built on negotiation and consensus between the MS are important milestones to understand the change in the inclusion of TCNs in policy-making. **The Expert Group on the views of migration, asylum and integration with the EC** was formed in line with the new 2021-2027 Action Plan.¹⁰⁴ The 24 members of the expert group, selected from a total of 354

⁹⁹ European Commission(2022) 'Expert Group Economic Migration', Available at: <https://ec.europa.eu/transparency/expert-groups-register/screen/expert-groups/consult?lang=en&do=groupDetail.groupDetail&groupID=3253> [Accessed on 28/11/22]

¹⁰⁰ European Commission (2022) 'Commission expert group on the Protection of Children in Migration', Available at: <https://ec.europa.eu/transparency/expert-groups-register/screen/expert-groups/consult?lang=en&do=groupDetail.groupDetail&groupID=3564&NewSearch=1&NewSearch=1> [Accessed on 28/11/2022]

¹⁰¹ European Commission (2018) 'European Migrant Advisory Board', Available at: <https://ec.europa.eu/futurium/en/inclusion-migrants-and-refugees/european-migrant-advisory-board-emab.html> [Accessed in 06/2022]

¹⁰² European Migrant Advisory Board (2019), 'Ask the People consultation report by the European Migrant Advisory Board', Available at: <https://ec.europa.eu/futurium/en/inclusion-migrants-and-refugees/ask-people-consultation-report-european-migrant-advisory-board.html> [Accessed in 06/2022]

¹⁰³ Virdee, S. and McGeever, B. (2018) 'Racism, Crisis, Brexit', *Ethnic and Racial Studies* 41(10): 1802-1819.

¹⁰⁴ European Commission (2020) 'Action plan on Integration and Inclusion 2021-2027', Available at: https://home-affairs.ec.europa.eu/system/files_en?file=2020-11/action_plan_on_integration_and_inclusion_2021-2027.pdf, p. 21; European Commission (2022) 'EXPERT GROUP ON THE VIEWS OF MIGRANTS IN THE FIELD OF MIGRATION, ASYLUM AND INTEGRATION (E03734)', Available at: <https://ec.europa.eu/transparency/expert-groups-register/screen/expert-groups/consult?do=groupDetail.groupDetail&groupID=3734> [Accessed in 06/2022]

applications, reside in 16 different Member States and represent migrants from a range of countries, including Turkey, Pakistan, Afghanistan, Syria, Brazil, Colombia, Senegal, Nigeria, Burundi, South Africa, Kenya and Kyrgyzstan. This is probably the most inclusive expert group so far. They held their first meeting in November 2020. While the participation of EU migrants in these groups is high, TCNs are less represented. In general, EU nationals moving to another EU Member State are better included in policy making.

Since 2014, EU-funded projects have also sought to increase migrants' participation in policy-making. In other words, the increased attention towards participation and inclusion of migrants in policy-making is reflected in the EU funding allocation. For instance, the ERASMUS+ programme "Empowering Immigrants' EU Social and Civic Participation through Innovative Media and Education"¹⁰⁵ aimed at supporting the integration of people with a migrant background through the delivery of online information on the EU Institutions, Access to Rights, Political Culture and Civic Participation, Employability and Cultural Heritage. Better informed of their rights and opportunities, migrants can participate at higher rates. Another EU-funded programme is MICADO¹⁰⁶ (pilot in Antwerp, Bologna, Hamburg and Madrid), completed in 2022, which exploits existing and new data to design digital services for the use of public administrations, engaged civic society, migrants and refugees.

Screening the **EU "Asylum, Migration and Integration Fund" (AMIF)** and its funded projects also reinforces the sentiment that the focus on migrant participation in policy making is increasing. Here are four examples of AMIF-funded projects supporting migrants' participation in policy-making.

- The INTEGRA project¹⁰⁷ aims to improve the long-term integration of TCNs in the European Union through sharing city-to-city knowledge and experiences, and cooperation between public and civic actors. The methodology meant that citizens were involved in the city audit, 'photovoice', allowing participants to express their point of view or represent their community by photographing scenes that relate to the audit themes. This enabled the inclusion of perspectives not often represented in policymaking.
- Under the slogan 'We all need new engagement',¹⁰⁸ this second project encourages the recognition of the invaluable contributions of immigrants from outside the EU

¹⁰⁵ IEUME (2022) 'Empowering Immigrants' EU Social and Civic Participation', Available at: <https://www.ieume.com/en/> [Consulted on 15/09/2022]

¹⁰⁶ European Commission (2019) 'Migrant Integration Cockpits and Dashboards. MICADO', Available at: <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/822717> [Accessed on 15/09/2022]

¹⁰⁷ European Commission (2020) 'AMIF Factsheets', Available at: https://www.sg.mai.gov.pt/FundosComunitarios/QFP20142020/Documents/Compilation_amif.pdf [Accessed in 08/2022]; Integra (n/a) 'City Integration Audit Toolkit', Available at: <https://www.integra-eu.net/city-audits/city-audit-toolkit.html> [Accessed in 08/2022]

¹⁰⁸ See European Commission (2020) 'AMIF Factsheets', Available at: https://www.sg.mai.gov.pt/FundosComunitarios/QFP20142020/Documents/Compilation_amif.pdf

who engage in civil society across the seven participating countries. This includes educational, cultural and social activities and decision-making frameworks, often among diaspora from the countries where they were born.

- Finally, Includities project is an AMIF-funded project in the multiannual framework programme 2014-2020, which aims at improving the integration of TCNs in middle-sized cities through city-to-city cooperation and with the involvement of migrant-led organisations or representatives. Eight cities, with varying degrees of integration-related experience, are involved and some of them constituted an advisory board of migrants in their municipal council (like in Levadia, Greece or Fuenlabrada in Spain).¹⁰⁹
- This report is funded by 2021-2027 AMIF, under the MILE Project.¹¹⁰ The MILE partners want to promote the active participation of migrants and refugees in local policy-making in areas that affect them, such as housing, education, culture, social rights, employment, and entrepreneurship.

The Russia-Ukraine war and the record numbers of displaced persons in a context of humanitarian crisis in 2022 is yet another critical event, leading to the EU activation of the temporary protection directive.

3.1.1 What progress has been made over time, and was there any regress?

It seems that there is an increased will of including TCNs and local governments / civil society. As reported by EMAB member Nour Machlah (interview 1), the EU has invited TCNs, notably refugee persons, to speak out and propose ideas to increase the efficiency of refugee policies. Yet, these public invitations are not followed by legislative proposals. EU nationals invited as experts do state the difficulty to move beyond a simple exercise of participation: because of the difficulty to reach a consensus between member states, proposals reaching expert groups and receiving feedback do not have the political flexibility to include the revisions proposed by experts (interview 6).

Hence, we consider that progress is still embryonic: if the 2021-2027 Action Plan highlights the importance of migrants' participation, the understanding of participation is still very contained to their integration in education, the labour market, or health services, rather than their inclusion in decision-making. The AMIF-funded projects we detailed above show that, if migrants are consulted through small exercises, TCNs are usually part of the projects for a short period of time, while the project consortium members are the ones building, fundraising, implementing and reporting on the projects. It is also worth noting that even though TCNs have been included in some consultative bodies, until they become citizens in an EU MS, they do not have the right to vote or to be elected at the European political and institutional level, and in general, have little political weight.

[Accessed in 08/2022] p. 57; and EMVI (n/a) 'Empowering Migrant Voices', Available at: <https://diaspora-participation.eu> [Accessed in 08/2022]

¹⁰⁹ Includities (2022) 'About the project', Available at: <https://includities.eu> [Accessed in 08/2022]

¹¹⁰ See our Webpage: <https://mile-project.eu>.

3.1.2 Are there any differences that can be observed across policy spheres?

Policy papers that we mentioned earlier in this report focus on training and education, employment and skills, health and housing. Funding of initiatives by AMIF - which gives us an indication on the consistency between policy narratives and policy enforcement – reinforces this trend. A good share of funded projects awarded from 2018 on¹¹¹ focus on training and education. Digital literacy in particular is seen as key to obtaining information and participating actively in decision-making. Another policy sphere is that of intercultural dialogue: unsurprisingly, migrants are seen as key partners in increasing information on rights and opportunities for inclusion and debunking myths and stereotypes. Additionally, within urban migration policymaking, there has also been progress in terms of participation and communication, as the INTEGRA project shows. Yet there is more focus and funding for local level projects which tend to be small-scale while there is less of large-scale projects that can make structural and long lasting changes. This shift was particularly acute when the EU URBAN programme which had significant funding for structural issues was ended in the 1990s to be replaced by URBACT,¹¹² a funding scheme and a methodology supporting exchange and transfer of knowledge across cities. URBACT funds pilot projects, small-scale schemes; and training and visiting trips for members.

¹¹¹ European Commission (2020) 'AMIF Factsheets', Available at:
https://www.sg.mai.gov.pt/FundosComunitarios/QFP20142020/Documents/Compilation_amif.pdf
[Accessed in 08/2022]

¹¹² Russeil, S. & Healy, A. (2015) 'Quelles expertises urbaines pour une Europe des villes: Le réseau Eurocities et ses experts', *Politique européenne*, 49: 54-83.

Table 1 Migrant inclusion in local policy making: timeline of progress in the European Union

When	Global event	EU event	Impact
1992		Maastricht Treaty establishing the European Union. The inclusivity of migrants in the European Union (EU) policy-making dates back to the 1992 Treaty of Maastrich, which formalised the rights of EU citizens to live, work and study in other EU countries. ¹¹³	Introducing new civic participation rights. As a result of the Maastricht Treaty, EU citizens have a range of rights when living in another member state, including the right to stand and vote in local, regional and EU elections. Millions of EU citizens exercise their right to live and work in other EU countries and, more generally, to travel freely between member states.
1995		The fourth EU enlargement. On 1 January 1995, Austria, Finland and Sweden joined the European Union. ¹¹⁴	Expanding the EU borders. This new enlargement changes the borders of the EU and its population (increase of 6.28%). This enlargement had little impact due to the wealth of these countries, but it was found that it started to show the issues related to the EU institutional structure, notably the size of the commission or the council's voting rules. ¹¹⁵
1999		The Tampere conference 1999. The Tampere conference in 1999 was a special meeting on the creation of an area of	Developing asylum and migration policy. The first point of the Tampere meeting was the creation of a common EU asylum and

¹¹³ European Council (2022) 'How Maastricht changed Europe', Available at: <https://www.consilium.europa.eu/en/maastricht-treaty/> [Accessed on 12/12/2022]

¹¹⁴ De Munter, A. (2021) 'The Enlargement of the Union', European Parliament, Available at: <https://www.europarl.europa.eu/factsheets/en/sheet/167/the-enlargement-of-the-union> [Accessed on 12/12/2022]

¹¹⁵ Bache, I. and George, S. (2006) *Politics in the European Union*, Oxford University Press. P 543-547.

		freedom, security and justice in the European Union. ¹¹⁶	migration policy, considering the rights and integration of third country nationals who want to access EU territory, including asylum seekers, while tackling illegal immigration. The economic and demographic benefits of migration are also highlighted.
2001	9/11 terrorist attacks. The question of integration of third country nationals grew bigger after 9/11, a global event which had an important effect on the migration-security nexus worldwide. ¹¹⁷		9/11 impact on migration discourse. In the aftermath of 9/11, scholars have shown that political discourses have reinforced the migration-security nexus. The question of long-term integration has become more central worldwide.
2002		Establishing National Contact Points on integration (NCPs). In the aftermath of 9/11, the Justice and Home Affairs Council of the EU requested in 2002 to establish the National Contact Points on integration (NCPs), creating a network of authorities at the EU level responsible for migrant integration. ¹¹⁸	Coordinating migration and integration policy. The European Council of June 2003 confirmed the mandate for establishing National Contact Points (NCPs) and invited the Commission to present Annual Reports on Migration and Integration. This led to a manual on best practices in 2004. The NCPs facilitate knowledge exchange to identify successful solutions to immigrant integration and seek to ensure policy coordination and coherence at the national level.

¹¹⁶ European Parliament (1999) 'TAMPERE EUROPEAN COUNCIL 15 AND 16 OCTOBER 1999 - PRESIDENCY CONCLUSIONS', Available at: https://www.europarl.europa.eu/summits/tam_en.htm [Accessed in 08/2022].

¹¹⁷ Faist, T. (2006) 'The migration-security nexus: International migration and security before and after 9/11', In: Bodemann, Y. M. and G. Yurdakul (eds) *Migration, Citizenship, Ethnos*, Palgrave Macmillan: New York, (pp. 103-119).

¹¹⁸ Commission of the European Communities (2005) 'A Common Agenda for Integration Framework for the Integration of Third-Country Nationals in the European Union', Available at: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=COM:2005:0389:FIN:en:PDF> [Accessed on 08/2022].

2004		<p>The fifth EU enlargement. On 1 May 2004, Malta, Cyprus, Estonia, Lithuania, Latvia, Poland, Czech Republic, Slovakia, Slovenia and Hungary joined the EU.¹¹⁹</p>	<p>Expanding the EU borders. This new enlargement changes the borders of the European Union east and south, and its population (increase of 19.57%, while the GDP only increased by 8.88%). 9 new official languages are included. The impact is not immediate on the labour market as free circulation is delayed until 2011, and despite the fears of mass migration, movements concern only 2% of the population.¹²⁰ At the institutional level though, the Justice and Home Affairs Council has suffered from the entry of these 8 countries with diverging national interests regarding migration, as the council operated at unanimity.</p>
2005		<p>Adopting the Hague Programme on integration.¹²¹ The Hague Programme was adopted by the European Council in November 2004 and underlined the need for greater coordination of national migrant integration policies and EU initiatives in this field.</p>	<p>Setting out migrant integration agenda. The Hague Programme sets the base for creating a common agenda on the integration of third country nationals, including the need to coordinate migrants' integration in the EU across member states.</p>

¹¹⁹ De Munter, A. (2021) 'The Enlargement of the Union', European Parliament, Available at: <https://www.europarl.europa.eu/factsheets/en/sheet/167/the-enlargement-of-the-union> [Accessed on 12/12/2022]

¹²⁰ European Citizen Action Service (2008). 'Who's afraid of the EU's Largest Enlargement? Report on the Impact of Bulgaria and Romania joining the union on Free Movement of People', Available at: <https://web.archive.org/web/20080614213440/http://www.libertysecurity.org/article1874.html> [Accessed on 20/12/2022]

¹²¹ Council of the European Union (2005). The Hague Programme: Strengthening freedom, security, and justice in the European Union. Available at: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/ALL/?uri=CELEX%3A52005XG0303%2801%29> [Accessed on 19/12/22]

2005		<p>Adopting a common framework for integration. A Common Agenda for Integration Framework for the Integration of Third-Country Nationals in the European Union was adopted in 2005.¹²²</p>	<p>Civic participation as key to integration. With this common agenda framework, member states agree that migrants' participation in the democratic process and in the formulation of integration policy, particularly at the local level, is important in supporting their integration. The framework encourages the creation of platforms of organisations and individuals, as well as the creation of the European Integration Network, and a new communication channel: the European Website for Integration (EWSI). EWSI comprises a network of national coordinators from all member states who collect and upload information regarding migrant integration in the respective member states.¹²³</p>
2007		<p>Introducing European funds for integration. To finance the work set out in the 2005 Common Agenda Integration Framework, between 2007-2013, the European Commission proposed new solidarity instruments, among them the European Fund for the Integration of third-</p>	<p>Funding the integration of immigrants. Allocation of EUR 825 million funds¹²⁵ for the integration of third-country nationals between 2007 and 2013.</p>

¹²² Favell, A. and Hansen, R. (2002) 'Markets against politics: Migration, EU enlargement and the idea of Europe', *Journal of Ethnic and Migration Studies*, 28(4): 581-601.

¹²³ Telephone interview with a country coordinator for EWSI, 19/09/2022.

¹²⁵ Legislation.gov.uk. (2007). Council Decision of 25 June 2007 establishing the European Fund for the Integration of third-country nationals for the period 2007 to 2013 as part of the General programme 'Solidarity and Management of Migration Flows' (2007/435/EC). Available at: <https://www.legislation.gov.uk/eudn/2007/435/2007-06-25> [Accessed on 12/12/2022]

		country nationals, ¹²⁴ which preceded the Asylum, Migration and Integration Fund that we know in 2022.	
2007		The sixth EU enlargement. On 1 January 2007, Bulgaria and Romania joined the EU. ¹²⁶	Expanding the EU borders. This new enlargement changes the borders of the European Union and its population (increase of 6.48%). Bulgaria's 18 and Romania's 35 observer MEPs became full voting representatives. Citizens of countries that migrated and were third country nationals become free movers within 7 years of the accession. It has been shown that this had positive effect on the labour market as there was more complementarity and flexibility than competition. ¹²⁷
2008	Onset of Global Financial Crisis. Great Recession, which started from a housing crisis and subprime crisis in the USA, and rapidly expanded to Europe and other regions of the world, leading to banking system crises to sovereign debt crises. The European Union, the European Central Bank, and		Recession impact on migration. A worldwide economic recession impacts EU member states, fragilizing the Eurozone, labour markets and reshuffling migration patterns in and out the EU. While migration may have reduced in some economic sectors affected by the recession, it was also shown "that immigrants have responded to changing labour shortages

¹²⁴ Legislation.gov.uk. (2007). Council Decision of 25 June 2007 establishing the European Fund for the Integration of third-country nationals for the period 2007 to 2013 as part of the General programme 'Solidarity and Management of Migration Flows' (2007/435/EC). Available at: <https://www.legislation.gov.uk/eudn/2007/435/2007-06-25> [Accessed on 12/12/2022]

¹²⁶ De Munter, A. (2021) 'The Enlargement of the Union', European Parliament, Available at: <https://www.europarl.europa.eu/factsheets/en/sheet/167/the-enlargement-of-the-union> [Accessed on 12/12/2022]

¹²⁷ Kahanec, M. and Zimmermann, K. F. (2016) 'EU post-enlargement migration and the Great Recession: lessons and policy implications', In: Kahanec, M., Zimmermann, K. (eds) *Labor Migration, EU Enlargement, and the Great Recession*, Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg, (pp. 419-445).

	the IMF (aka Troika) enforced austerity plans in several European countries. The impact on public spending, salaries and tax levels has had long-lasting effects.		across EU member states, occupations and sectors at least as much and in many cases more flexibly than natives". ¹²⁸
2009		Lisbon Treaty introduces the EU migration policy. With the 1992 Maastricht Treaty, migration policy-making was an intergovernmental 'pillar'. But it is the 2009 Lisbon Treaty (articles 77–80) that sets out the EU's competences on borders, asylum, and immigration. ¹²⁹	Sharing of responsibility for migration. The EU committed to 'the principle of solidarity and fair sharing of responsibility' as a governing principle for migration policy. Migration was brought entirely under the community method, empowering the European Parliament and European Court of Justice. The Lisbon Treaty also reinforces citizen engagement in all policy areas.
2011		Introducing integration within the Eurobarometer survey. The first ever Eurobarometer on Migrant Integration was conducted in 2011. ¹³⁰ The Eurobarometer is a series of regular public opinion surveys carried out across EU member states on a range of topics related to the EU.	Consulting EU residents on integration. European residents have been consulted regularly on migration and integration issues through the Eurobarometer survey since 2011. The first ever Eurobarometer on migrant integration included qualitative discussions with EU citizens as well as third country nationals.

¹²⁸ Kahanec, M. and Guzi, M. (2017) 'How immigrants helped EU labor markets to adjust during the Great Recession', *International Journal of Manpower*, 38(7): 996-1015.

¹²⁹ Hampshire, J. (2016) 'European migration governance since the Lisbon treaty: introduction to the special issue', *Journal of Ethnic and Migration Studies*, 42(4): 537-553.

¹³⁰ European Commission (2011) 'Eurobarometer on Migrant Integration', Available at: https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/en/MEMO_11_529 [Accessed on 06/2022]

2013		The seventh EU enlargement. On 1 July 2013, Croatia joined the EU. ¹³¹	Expanding the EU borders. This new enlargement changes the borders of the EU and its population (increase of 0.85%). Citizens of Croatia became free movers between 2013 and 2020, depending on the EU member state. Negotiations were tougher than expected due to a border disagreement with Slovenia.
2014		Introducing Asylum, Migration and Integration Fund. The first round of the new Asylum, Migration and Integration Fund (AMIF) was introduced in 2014 for the 2014-2020 period.	Increasing funding for migrant integration. The former European Fund for the Integration of third-country nationals (2007-2013) is replaced by the Asylum, Migration and Integration Fund (2014-2020) with the budget of EUR 3.137 billion ¹³² , almost four times more than the former 825 million Fund for the Integration of Third-Country Nationals.
2015	The 'refugee crisis' in Europe. A significantly increased movement of refugees and asylum seekers, arriving at the European borders in 2015 was		EU response and governance crisis. The EU responded with a series of controversial mechanisms, such as re-bordering by several member states and the EU-Turkey refugee return agreement. ¹³⁴ In 2016, the European Commission began reforming the Common

¹³¹ De Munter, A. (2021) 'The Enlargement of the Union', European Parliament', European Parliament, Available at: <https://www.europarl.europa.eu/factsheets/en/sheet/167/the-enlargement-of-the-union> [Accessed on 12/12/2022]

¹³² European Commission (2022) 'EU funds for migrant integration 2021-2027', Available at: https://ec.europa.eu/migrant-integration/funding/eu-funds-2021-2027-period_en [Accessed on 20/12/22]

¹³⁴ European Parliament (2022) 'Legislative train. EU-Turkey Statement and Action Plan', Available at: <https://www.europarl.europa.eu/legislative-train/carriage/eu-turkey-statement-action-plan/report?sid=6101> [Accessed on 06/2022]

	generally understood and managed as a crisis. ¹³³		European Asylum System. ¹³⁵ At the same time, we see a reinforcement of the role of cities and networks of cities in addressing reception of refugees. ¹³⁶
2015		Creating expert group on economic migration. The refugee crisis triggered a governance crisis in the EU which led to the creation of several expert groups on migration-related matters, such as the 'Expert Group Economic Migration'. ¹³⁷	Consulting stakeholders on economic migration. The 'Expert Group Economic Migration' was formed in 2015 to consult representatives of civil society organisations, such as trade unions, academics and chambers of commerce, as well as individuals, on the EU policy proposals regarding labour migration.
2016		Creating a new agenda on migrant inclusion. The 'Urban Agenda for the EU Partnership on Inclusion of Migrants and Refugees (2016-2019) ¹³⁸ was created in 2016 as one of the priority areas of the wider 'Urban Agenda for the EU' which launched to promote cooperation between	Improving migrant inclusion and civic participation. The Urban Agenda Partnership on Inclusion of Migrants and Refugees was created with the goal to improve migrant and refugee inclusion in the medium and long term. A few consultation and capacity-building mechanisms were developed under the

¹³³ Bojadžijev, M. and Mezzadra, S. (2015) "Refugee crisis" or crisis of European migration policies? FocaalBlog post series on migration and the refugee crisis. Available at: https://syllabus.pirate.care/_preview/library/Manuela%20Bojadzijev/_Refugee%20crisis_%20or%20crisis%20of%20European%20migration%20policies_%20465/_Refugee%20crisis_%20or%20crisis%20of%20European%20mig%20-%20Manuela%20Bojadzijev.pdf. [Accessed on: 14/12/2022]

¹³⁵ European Commission (2022) 'Common European Asylum System', Available at: https://home-affairs.ec.europa.eu/policies/migration-and-asylum/common-european-asylum-system_en [Accessed on 06/2022].

¹³⁶ Lacroix, T. (2021) 'Migration-related city networks: a global overview', *Local Government Studies*, 1-21.

¹³⁷ European Commission (2022) 'Expert Group Economic Migration', Available at: <https://ec.europa.eu/transparency/expert-groups-register/screen/expert-groups/consult?lang=en&do=groupDetail.groupDetail&groupID=3253> [Accessed on 28/11/22]

¹³⁸ Stürner-Siovit, J. and Heimann, C. (2022) 'The EU Urban Partnership on Inclusion: Institutionalizing Local–Supranational Integration Governance', *International Migration Review*, First published online June 22, 2022.

		member states, cities, the European Commission and other stakeholders to improve the quality of life, innovation and growth in urban areas while tackling social challenges.	partnership including, the European Migrant Advisory Board (EMAB), the Urban Academy, and the citizens' forum Futurium on issues related to inclusion.
2017		Creating expert group on unaccompanied minors. The 'Commission Expert Group on the Protection of Children in Migration' ¹³⁹ was created in 2017 while increased numbers of children reached Europe alone. The group brings together migration experts from member states.	Consulting stakeholders on unaccompanied minors. Following the record number of unaccompanied minors reaching the EU, the 'Commission Expert Group on the Protection of Children in Migration' was created to address the particular challenges met by migrant children. At each of the 9 meetings of the group, a specific issue is addressed, and recommendations are formulated in order to be disseminated in decision-making circles and other expert fora. At the last meeting in February 2022, ¹⁴⁰ recommendations made concerned external support needed by the guardians of unaccompanied migrant.
2018		Creating an advisory board of migrants. The European Migrant Advisory Board (EMAB) was created in 2018 under the Urban Agenda Partnership on Inclusion of Migrants and Refugees to provide a consultation mechanism, comprising individual migrants as advisors. EMAB is a	Including migrants in policy making. The European Migrant Advisory Board (EMAB) facilitates greater inclusion of migrant voices in policy making. For example, the board members speak on migration issues at the European Parliament and, in 2018, conducted a consultation with migrants and refugees 'Ask

¹³⁹ European Commission (2022) 'Commission expert group on the Protection of Children in Migration', Available at: <https://ec.europa.eu/transparency/expert-groups-register/screen/expert-groups/consult?lang=en&do=groupDetail.groupDetail&groupID=3564&NewSearch=1&NewSearch=1> [Accessed on 28/11/2022]

¹⁴⁰ DG-HOME (2022) '9th Meeting of the HOME Expert Group on the Protection of Children in Migration'.

		self-made group of nine advisors, all third country nationals residing in different EU member states, who work together to increase the participation of refugees and immigrants in policy making.	the People', the results of which are published on the European Commission website. ¹⁴¹ However, such consultations are generally not followed by legislative proposals and there is no established mechanism to ensure institutional responsiveness to migrants' requests. Additionally, some barriers to migrants' equal access to EMAB remain, such as the requirement to speak good English and to understand the jargon accessible only to well educated. ¹⁴²
2020	Global outbreak of COVID-19 pandemic. The COVID-19 pandemic is a global outbreak of coronavirus – an infectious disease. First detected in China in late 2019, the virus spread quickly across the world. The World Health Organisation declared it a public health emergency in 2020. ¹⁴³		COVID-19 impact on the EU. The onset of Covid 19 has led to re-bordering within the EU – intra-EU movements were stopped or subjected to new controls and exceptions. This generated changes in migration patterns ¹⁴⁴ – such as reduced migration flows – and a new economic recession in the EU, with the energy sector being more at risk. The pandemic had a disproportionate effect on migrant communities who often held “essential” jobs, and had more difficulties to isolate from contagious persons. The 2021-

¹⁴¹ European Migrant Advisory Board (2019) 'Ask the People consultation report by the European Migrant Advisory Board', Available at: <https://ec.europa.eu/futurium/en/inclusion-migrants-and-refugees/ask-people-consultation-report-european-migrant-advisory-board.html> [Accessed on 06/2022].

¹⁴² Interviews with several members of EMAB in 2022.

¹⁴³ World Health Organisation (2022) 'Coronavirus disease (COVID-19) pandemic: Overview', Available at: <https://www.who.int/europe/emergencies/situations/covid-19> [Accessed on 22/11/2022]

¹⁴⁴ Migration Data Portal (2022) 'Migration relevant data for the Covid-19 pandemic', Available at: <https://www.migrationdataportal.org/themes/migration-data-relevant-covid-19-pandemic> [Accessed on 20/12/2022]

			2027 Action Plan was developed in this period, introducing an increase in funding for migration and integration under Asylum, Migration and Integration Fund.
2020		<p>Introducing action plan on integration. The Action Plan on Integration and Inclusion (2021-2027) was released by the European Commission in November 2020. While national governments are primarily responsible for the design of integration and social policies (education, employment, housing, healthcare), the plan asserts that the EU plays a fundamental role in supporting them through funding, developing practical tools, coordinating actions and establishing relevant partnerships.</p>	<p>Strengthening migrant inclusion in policy making. Following the drafting of the 2021-2027 Action Plan on Integration and Inclusion, the ‘Expert Group on the views of migrants in the field of migration, asylum and integration’¹⁴⁵ was created to increase the participation of third country nationals in consultative groups at the EU level. The 24 members of the expert group, selected from a total of 354 applications, reside in 16 different member states and represent migrants from a range of countries outside the EU. Additionally, the new plan¹⁴⁶ aims at ‘mainstreaming gender and including women’, highlighting particular challenges faced by migrant women in areas of employment and access to health services. The plan takes into account the intersectional nature of specific challenges faced by migrants.</p>

¹⁴⁵ European Commission (2020) ‘Action plan on Integration and Inclusion 2021-2027’, Available at: https://home-affairs.ec.europa.eu/system/files/en?file=2020-11/action_plan_on_integration_and_inclusion_2021-2027.pdf, p. 21; European Commission (2022) ‘EXPERT GROUP ON THE VIEWS OF MIGRANTS IN THE FIELD OF MIGRATION, ASYLUM AND INTEGRATION (E03734)’, Available at: <https://ec.europa.eu/transparency/expert-groups-register/screen/expert-groups/consult?do=groupDetail.groupDetail&groupID=3734> [Accessed on 06/2022]

¹⁴⁶ European Commission (2020) ‘The EC reveals its new EU Action Plan on Integration and Inclusion (2021-2027)’, Available at: https://ec.europa.eu/migrant-integration/news/ec-reveals-its-new-eu-action-plan-integration-and-inclusion-2021-2027_en [Accessed on 06/2022].

2021		<p>Expanding Asylum, Migration and Integration Fund. The new round of Asylum, Migration and Integration Fund (AMIF) was introduced in 2021, with its budget expanded substantially, tripled from EUR 3.137 billion for 2014-2020 to EUR 9.9 billion for 2021-2027).¹⁴⁷</p>	<p>Increasing focus on migrants' civic participation. Looking at the Asylum, Migration and Integration Fund (AMIF) and its funded projects for the periods 2014-20 and 2021-27 reinforces the view that the focus on migrant participation in policy making is increasing. Projects such as 'INTEGRA', 'Inclucities' and 'MILE' all support migrants' participation in policy making.</p>
2022	<p>Russia-Ukraine war. In February 2022, the declaration of war of Russia to Ukraine triggered mass migration.</p>		<p>Impact of Russia-Ukraine war on Europe. In June 2022, there were 5.5 million Ukrainian refugees in Europe, 3.6 million having received temporary protection.¹⁴⁸ The EU activated the 'temporary protection' directive,¹⁴⁹ a common system provided in the Treaty of Lisbon (2009) and the CEAS, and adopted in 2011, to grant one-year protection in case of massive flux of displaced people due to armed conflict. It was never activated by EU member states until 2022. The European Commission decided for a Cohesion's Action for Refugees in Europe (CARE), committing over EUR 370 billion of cohesion funds.</p>

¹⁴⁷ European Commission (2022) 'EU funds for migrant integration 2021-2027'. Available at: https://ec.europa.eu/migrant-integration/funding/eu-funds-2021-2027-period_en [Accessed on 20/12/22]

¹⁴⁸ UNHCR (2022) 'Ukraine Refugee Situation', Available at: <https://data.unhcr.org/en/situations/ukraine> [Accessed on 06/2022].

¹⁴⁹ OFPRA (2022) 'OFPRA and asylum in Europe', Available at: <https://www.ofpra.gouv.fr/en/ofpra-and-asylum-europe> [Accessed on 20/12/22]

**Migrant
Integration through
Locally designed
Experiences**

3.2 Best practice of migrant inclusion in policy making

Box 1 Expert Group on the views of migrants in the field of migration, asylum and integration¹⁵⁰

Target group

Members can be: individuals appointed in their personal capacity who are to act independently (Type A); individuals appointed to represent a common interest shared by stakeholders in a particular policy area (Type B); organisations representing the interests of migrants (Type C). They shall have good knowledge of English, have relevant experience in migration, asylum and integration, and be well connected with a wider network of migrant organisations and communities. Moreover, DG HOME may also invite some experts to take part in the discussion on an ad hoc basis.

Objectives

(1) To advise the Commission on its general strategy and specific initiatives in this field, by actively involving migrants, asylum applicants and refugees to ensure effective and tailored policy design and implementation; and (2) to assist the Commission both in relation to the implementation of existing Union legislation, programmes and policies, and to the preparation of legislative proposals and policy initiatives.

Key features

Created in 2020 by DG HOME, the mission of this expert group is to provide DG HOME advice and expertise on policies in the field of migration, asylum and integration of migrants. Since its creation, the group meets regularly at least two times per year, after having received some material in advance. It is composed of 20 members appointed for a period of 2 years and selected via a call for applications.

Results achieved

The group adopts its opinions, recommendations or reports by consensus. By December 2022, the group has met seven times since its creation; the minutes and draft agendas of the meetings are made public on the EC website. In October 2022, the group has met in person, in Brussels, for the first time.

¹⁵⁰ European Commission (2022) 'Expert group on the views of migrants in the field of migration, asylum and integration (E03734), available at: <https://ec.europa.eu/transparency/expert-groups-register/screen/expert-groups/consult?lang=en&do=groupDetail.groupDetail&groupID=3734> [accessed on 25/11/2022]

Box 2 European Website on Integration (EWSI)¹⁵¹

Target group

Specifically addressing policy makers and practitioners, the website is user friendly and open to the public; users can navigate it across devices, including smartphones and tablets. In the future, an interactive online tool allowing users to explore the progress made on the EU action plan on integration and inclusion (2021-2027) will also be published.

Objectives

The website is the only EU-wide source which brings up-to-date information and good practices on migrant integration, through the collection of legal and policy developments, good practices, funding opportunities, country fiches and statistics and analytical articles, on the theme of integration and inclusion.

Key features

Launched in 2009, EWSI is the most comprehensive information website on migrant integration in the EU. It is available in 3 languages: English, French and German. It is an initiative of the European Commission and falls under the responsibility of the Directorate-General Home Affairs and Migration (DG HOME), who is assisted by the Migration Policy Group (MPG). MPG leads on both the content and technical development of the website, and is in charge of the website's day-to-day content maintenance. Moreover, it manages a network of 27 Country Coordinators, experienced integration experts who represent their respective country. They are tasked with uploading national-level content, collecting information used to produce EU-wide analyses and promoting the website in their respective countries.

Results achieved

Today, EWSI collects 14,000 country updates and over 1,300 successful integration practices from across the EU.

The main results or impact achieved are:

- Publication of news, documents, and events on integration
- Large collection of good practices on integration
- Special pan-EU analyses, as the one in 2021 on the mapping of key migrant-led organisations across the EU
- An overview of the EU's work on migrant integration
- Dedicated [funding information](#) about EU and other funds available for integration and ongoing financing calls
- Country-specific [pages](#) summarising all about the governance of migrant integration in each of the EU countries
- A monthly newsletter on the latest on integration.

¹⁵¹ European Commission (2022) 'European Website on Integration', Available at: https://ec.europa.eu/migrant-integration/home_en [Accessed on 30/11/2022]

Box 3 FAST-CARE Fund (Flexible Assistance for Territories - Cohesion's Action for Refugees in Europe)¹⁵²

Target group

All Member States - proportionally to their national allocations - would benefit from the additional pre-financing. Moreover, it directly interests LRGs and civil society organisations.

Objectives

Help the EU Member States to alleviate the consequences of the Russian invasion of Ukraine, by providing additional support for those welcoming and integrating displaced people. After the adoption of the CARE - allowing Member States and regions to provide emergency support to people fleeing from Russia's invasion of Ukraine as well as to those receiving them - the Commission decided to enhance its support by offering further flexibility through the FAST-CARE funds.

Key features

The proposal extends the support already provided under Cohesion's Action for Refugees in Europe (CARE), by introducing new provisions for additional flexibility and maximum efficiency of cohesion policy investment. Indeed, the proposal allows national authorities to finance both emergency and longer-term integration measures (e.g., education or housing infrastructure, etc.) of all TCNs or stateless persons, by increasing the EU pre-financing payments to €3.5 billion for programmes receiving support from the ERDF, the European Social Fund Plus - ESF+ and the Cohesion Fund. Moreover, it addresses 30% of the expenditure on refugees for local authorities and civil society organisations, who are at the forefront in providing assistance in welcoming and integrating refugees.

Results achieved

The expected results of FAST-CARE are at an early, medium and longer-term stage. In the short term, it will facilitate financing of first reception and immediate relief of people fleeing the war in Ukraine. At a second stage, it may support welcome and orientation measures such as accommodation, construction or refurbishing of reception centres, accommodation and staff costs for running the facilities and integration activities. In the longer-term, access may be offered to healthcare,

¹⁵² European Council (2022) 'FAST-CARE: Council adopts negotiating mandate on further help for refugees from Ukraine and on addressing the consequences of Russia's aggression', Available at: https://www.consilium.europa.eu/en/press/press-releases/2022/07/20/fast-care-council-adopts-negotiating-mandate-on-further-help-for-refugees-from-ukraine-and-on-addressing-the-consequences-of-russia-s-aggression/?utm_source=dsms-auto&utm_medium=email&utm_campaign=FAST-CARE%3a+Council+adopts+negotiating+mandate+on+further+help+for+refugees+from+Ukraine+and+on+addressing+the+consequences+of+Russia%u2019s+aggression [Accessed on 28/11/2022]; News European Parliament (15/09/2022) 'FAST-CARE: MEPs fast-track EU support in response to Russia's war in Ukraine', Available at: <https://www.europarl.europa.eu/news/en/press-room/20220912IPR40205/fast-care-meps-fast-track-eu-support-in-response-to-russia-s-war-in-ukraine> [Accessed on 28/11/2022]

psychological care and community-based support, childcare, social housing, access to the labour market, education and training.

Box 4

Q: I want to know more about successful EU-funded projects which have addressed the participation of migrant individuals and communities in policy-making. Where do I look?

A: This is the directory of EU-funded projects: <https://cordis.europa.eu/projects/en>, Using keywords, you can find projects relevant to your field, which can inspire you to draw your own project.

In this report, we have listed a few projects addressing issues of political/policy-making participation:

- Empowering Migrants' Voices (EMVI)
- Empowering Immigrants' EU Social and Civic Participation through Innovative Media for Education (IEUME)
- Integration of Third Country Nationals Through Urban Partnerships (INTEGRA)
- Maximising Migrants' Contribution to Society (MAX)
- Migrant Integration Cockpits and Dashboards (MICADO)
- European Refugees Oral History Project (Specially Unknown)
- Urban Academy.

And we have listed a few networks where leaders/practitioners exchange and/or lobby together on these issues:

- Cities and Regions for Integration initiative
- Eurocities
- Intercultural Cities Programme
- Mediterranean City-to-City Migration (MC2CM)
- SHARE network
- URBACT.

4 ENGAGEMENT OF MIGRANT COMMUNITIES IN POLICY MAKING

4.1 European strategy for local participation

4.1.1 Does the EU have an explicitly written strategy to promote participation by residents in public decision making irrespective of their nationality / background?

Depending on the specific context and field of interest, the concept of participation can be interpreted from different perspectives and be operationalised in various ways.¹⁵³ In this report, we refer to the engagement of communities and individuals in decisions that directly affect them, considering the voting rights as its maximum expression. In the European context, when we talk about local participation of residents *in general*, we refer to the **EU Cohesion Policy**¹⁵⁴, which represents almost a third of the total EU budget (EUR 372 billion for 2021-2027) and one of the EU's largest investment policies. Indeed, the idea that increasing citizens' engagement positively contributes to public governance and more transparency and accountability, is a shared one. The importance of promoting citizen engagement has been recognised and reinforced in the Lisbon Treaty.

The objective of the Cohesion policy for the programming period 2021-2027 is the achievement of a competitive, fair and sustainable Europe and citizens' engagement is one of the priorities. Towards this direction, in February 2020, the Commission - under the political leadership of Commissioner for Cohesion and Reforms, Elisa Ferreira - organised a high-level conference with the name "Engaging citizens for good governance in Cohesion Policy", where delegates discussed policy not only *for* but also *with* citizens. However, the report of the Conference does not mention migrants.

Moreover, from July 2020 to December 2021, the Commission (DG REGIO) and the OECD partnered to work with five selected authorities in the EU on how to engage more closely with citizens and civil society. The report (published in March 2022¹⁵⁵) mentions migrants twice among the excluded groups whose inclusion in the decision-making process would have a positive impact for inclusion and diversity as well as for the fight against exclusion and marginalisation, calling public authorities to lower barriers to participation. In addition, the Commission organises a Structured Dialogue with stakeholders that represent the partners at Union level in order to bring EU funds and Cohesion Policy closer to civil society, to assist the Commission in the development of the policy in different areas of expertise and to discuss the implementation of EU funds.

¹⁵³ Aryeh-Adjei, A.A, Afotey Anang, S. and Osei-Adusah, D. (2022) 'Local Participation in Community: Based Development Projects in Ghana', *International Journal of Social Ecology and Sustainable Development* 13(1).

¹⁵⁴ European Commission (2022) 'How to make citizens active participants in the governance of EU Cohesion policy', Available at: https://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/en/policy/how/improving-investment/citizens-participation/ [Accessed on 15/09/2022]

¹⁵⁵ OECD Publishing (2022) 'Engaging citizens in cohesion policy: DG REGIO and OECD pilot project final report', Available at: <https://www.oecd.org/italy/engaging-citizens-in-cohesion-policy-486e5a88-en.htm> [Accessed on: 15/09/2022]

A series of funds and financial instruments support the EU cohesion policy. Among the priorities for 2021-2027 EU cohesion policy there is a more social and inclusive Europe, a policy objective to which the European Social Fund+ (ESF+) is dedicated and to which the European Regional Development Fund (ERDF) contributes. It is interesting to note the way in which the instruments and funds of the Cohesion Policy were used to respond to the huge fleet of people from Ukraine following the Russian invasion. Indeed, the European Commission decided for a Cohesion's Action for Refugees in Europe (CARE) of over 370 billion Euros of cohesion funds. This fund is aimed at supporting MS and regions by providing emergency assistance to people fleeing from Russia's invasion of Ukraine. MS may use this funding to develop tailor-made solutions for the long-term integration of people with a migrant background, through investments in housing, education, employment, health, social inclusion and care. CARE complements support from the AMIF and other funding sources.

More specifically, considering the local-level participation of migrants in decision-making processes, we analyse the **2021-2027 Action Plan on Integration and Inclusion**. Recognising that the challenge of integration and inclusion is particularly relevant for both newcomers and EU citizens with a migrant background, who play a relevant role in the European economy and society, the Plan aims at increasing migrants' participation in the following areas: education and training, employment, health, and housing.

It is worth noting that integration discourses in this document do not provide for the accession to political rights (voting, and being elected).¹⁵⁶ However, the Plan addresses the need for fostering participation of the migrant population and its encounters with the host society. More specifically, it sets out the goal of having more migrants and EU citizens with a migrant background participate in consultative and decision-making processes at local, regional, national and European levels as a means of empowering them and ensuring that integration and inclusion policies are more effective and reflect real needs. The following sections of the report will mainly focus on this Action Plan.

4.1.2 Does the strategy commit to (1) making this a two-way process of communication; (2) responding to the voice of residents; and (3) giving voice to informal participatory action as well as formal processes such as consultations?

The Action Plan defines integration and inclusion as a two-way "societal process" where responsibility relies on many groups: migrants, host communities, public authorities and institutions, social and economic partners, civil society organisations, religious communities and the private sector. It further recognises that "developing welcoming, diverse and inclusive societies is a process that needs the engagement of both migrants and the receiving society". In this sense, the Commission commits itself to build strong and long-term multi-stakeholder partnerships at various levels of governance in order to maximise the effectiveness of its actions. It also calls for the creation of places and

¹⁵⁶ See <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A52020DC0758&qid=1632299185798>.

opportunities for migrants and local communities to meet and interact, with the final aim of creating more inclusive and cohesive societies.

The Action Plan calls for “building capacity of local and regional authorities to involve local communities in the design and implementation of integration measures.” Moreover, it is worth to outline that the propositions of the 2021-2027 Action Plan are also the result of broad consultations the Commission had with various actors (June-October 2020), including civil society organisations, international organisations, migrants, and refugees.

Along with the support for informal participatory action in various areas, the Action Plan calls for launching partnerships and starting political dialogues among the various tiers of government and community stakeholders, in order to support Local and Regional governments (LRGs). The Commission commits itself to support civil society by engaging in regular consultations and dialogue with civil society and diaspora organisations. Moreover, in using EU funding for integration, it encourages MS to involve local and regional authorities, civil society organisations - including those representing migrants and diaspora- and social and economic partners in preparing, revising, implementing and monitoring programmes for the 2021-2027 EU funds (AMIF, ESF+, ERDF).

It is worth to mention some of the actors that were consulted by DG HOME in the drafting of the 2021-2027 Action Plan: firstly, a public consultation¹⁵⁷ was conducted and led to over 800 answers, 63% of which coming from individuals, 37% from organisations. Secondly, some organisations were reached directly through targeted consultation meetings¹⁵⁸, including European Integration Network (EIN); representatives of LRGs (Assembly of European Regions, European Association for Local Democracy, Council of European Municipalities and Regions, Conference of Peripheral Maritime Regions, Eurocities, Committee of Regions); some civil society organisations, as European Council on Refugees and Exiles, European Network Against Racism, European Network of Migrant Women, OXFAM and New Women Connectors. For a complete list of the consulted stakeholders, please follow this [link](#).

We will develop further the different consultation processes that exist, but we might already note the activity of several expert groups regularly consulted by DG-HOME, including the most recent Expert Group on the views of migrants in the fields of migration, asylum and integration.

¹⁵⁷ European Commission (2020) ‘Analysis of the responses to the public consultation on the integration and inclusion of migrants and people with a migrant background’, Available at: https://ec.europa.eu/home-affairs/system/files_en?file=2020-11/synthesis_analysis_responses_public_consultation_integration_inclusion_2020.pdf [Consulted in 06/2022]

¹⁵⁸ European Commission (2020) ‘Report on the consultation on the integration and inclusion of migrants and people with a migrant background’, Available at: https://home-affairs.ec.europa.eu/system/files_en?file=2020-11/summary_of_consultations_in_view_of_the_action_plan_on_integration_and_inclusion.pdf [Consulted in 06/2022]

4.1.3 Does the strategy adopt an intersectional approach seeking to tackle multiple axes of inequality simultaneously to promote local participation? Are some axes of inequality considered as principal?

The 2021-2027 Action Plan adopts an intersectional approach; it clearly states that one of its key principles and values is mainstreaming gender and anti-discrimination priorities, and that therefore it will consider “the combination of personal characteristics, such as gender, racial or ethnic origin, religion or belief, sexual orientation and disability that can represent specific challenges for migrants”. The Plan makes multiple references to other frameworks, such as the forthcoming action plan to implement the European Pillar for Social Rights and the EU’s anti-racism action plan 2020-2025, the EU Roma strategic framework for equality, inclusion and participation, the LGBTQI+ Equality Strategy 2020-2025, the strategy to combat antisemitism, the EU citizenship report, the forthcoming Strategy on the rights of persons with disabilities, and the Gender Equality Strategy 2020-2025. Throughout the action plan, particular attention is called for women (employment and health), children (education), people with some form of disability (education).

4.1.4 Is the intersectional approach to EU participation adopted across different policy spheres?

The intersectional approach is adopted across different policy spheres; for example, in relation to education and training, particular attention is drawn towards migrant children with disabilities, but the gender perspective is not considered. In employment and skills, migrant women and migrants with disabilities are mentioned. In reference to health, the gender perspective is included. Finally, when talking about housing, no other grounds of discrimination are explored.

4.1.5 Does the EU have any existing structures for political / civic participation of the migrant population?

There are a number of existing participation mechanisms at the EU level to facilitate the inclusion of migrants in policy making:

The **European Migration Forum (EMF)**¹⁵⁹, since 2015 (it developed from the European Integration Forum, 2009-2014), is a forum co-organised by DG HOME and the European Economic and Social Committee (EESC) that has the aim of enhancing coordination and cooperation between the main actors involved in the European multi-level governance of migration. Every year, it gathers together representatives from EU institutions and civil society organisations, with the aim of exchanging ideas and best practices, and of discussing the main priorities with decision-makers. Among the participants of some of the editions held from 2015, there is the Expert Group on the views of migrants in the

¹⁵⁹ European Commission (2022) ‘Migration and Home Affairs. European Migration Forum (EMF)’, Available at: https://home-affairs.ec.europa.eu/policies/migration-and-asylum/legal-migration-and-integration/european-migration-forum-emf_en [Accessed on 20/09/2022]

field of migration, asylum and integration, European Council on Refugees and Exiles and New Women Connectors, among others.

The **European Migrant Advisory Board (EMAB)**, established by the Inclusion partnership of the Urban Agenda of the EU, is a self-led group of nine advisors with refugee and immigrant backgrounds, working together to increase the participation of refugees and immigrants in different policy-making processes affecting their access to rights. As its former member explained, it was created between the end of 2017 and early 2019 and gathered together migrants and refugees from different countries, including Germany, The Netherlands, Spain and Greece. Its aim was to work on a meaningful participation of migrants and refugees, instead of their tokenization: “it is important to have migrants and refugees in decision-making roles, where they can advise and talk, fighting to have equal roles and to make their voices heard” (interview 4). In 2018, EMAB conducted the consultation “Ask the People” on a wide array of issues, picked by Board’s members among the ones considered urgent by the Commission (interview 4). Initially, EMAB’s members worked together for one year and a half, studying the agenda of the Commission and choosing some of its topics to work on (interview 4).

The **2021-2027 Action Plan** provides various participation mechanisms. First, actors of the civil society that were consulted by DG HOME for the drafting of the Action Plan and who represent migrants and refugees, as: New Women Connectors for inclusion and social justice¹⁶⁰ (2019), a non-profit organisation led by migrant and refugee women; and the European Network of Migrant women¹⁶¹ (2012), a migrant-women-led feminist, secular, non-partisan platform that advocates for the rights, freedoms and dignity of migrant, refugee and ethnic minority women and girls in Europe. Second, it supported the creation of **the Expert Group on the views of migrants in the fields of migration, asylum and integration** by the EC to actively involve asylum applicants and refugees in the design and implementation of policies in this field. Composed of persons with a migrant background, the group is aimed at ensuring effective and tailored policy design and implementation (see Box 1 for more detail).

Programmes supported by EU funding (such as AMIF, and other mechanisms), including networks of cities for knowledge transfer and advocacy, which require participation mechanisms as funding criteria (also called European transnational city networks) include: the Cities and Regions for Integration Initiative (CRII), which provides a political platform for the European mayors and regional leaders to showcase positive examples of integration of migrants and refugees, share relevant information and promote diversity as an added value to building inclusive cities and ensuring social cohesion. Here, the participation of migrants and refugees is not envisaged. The SHARE

¹⁶⁰ New Women Connectors (2021) ‘About’, Available at:
<https://www.newwomenconnectors.com/about> [Accessed in 08/2022]

¹⁶¹ European Network of Migrant Women (2021) ‘Who we are’, Available at:
<https://www.migrantwomennetwork.org> [Accessed in 08/2022]

Network¹⁶², created in 2012 by the International Catholic Migration Commission, is aimed at supporting regions, cities, towns, and rural communities interested in welcoming refugees and migrants, through various funded projects. In its strategy, it envisions the participation of migrants and refugees. Other networks worth-mentioning are the Mediterranean City-to-City Migration (MC2CM) implemented by the International Centre for Migration Policy Development (ICMPD),¹⁶³ Eurocities,¹⁶⁴ and several networks of URBACT.¹⁶⁵

The European Commission-based **Futurium** is a platform dedicated to Europeans discussing EU policies. Citizens can sign in and take part in foras, categorised by group. In Futurium, under the Urban Agenda for the EU, a specific group exists dealing with the “Inclusion of migrants and refugees”.¹⁶⁶ The Inclusion partnership of the Urban Agenda for the EU is also at the origin of the **Urban Academy**: “The Urban Academy offers a strategic learning environment through thematic modules to share successful (and less successful) experiences and to create networks of peers working on similar issues across Europe. It brings together practitioners and policy-makers working on integration at the local, regional and national level, with a focus on cities.”¹⁶⁷ Two thematic sessions were organised in 2018, both on issues related to cities and integration.

We interviewed some members of the groups that directly involve migrants, people with a migrant background and/or refugees. Overall, it seems that participation of migrants and refugees at the EU level is limited by two factors. First, only those who are already settled for a few years, possess a good command of English, or have time / means to participate do so, which means that wider representation of the diversity of migrants is potentially low. Second, the participation mechanisms are often more of a “paper trail”,¹⁶⁸ with real political change inaccessible. Further investigation into the political participation at the EU level of TCNs and/or EU citizens with migrant backgrounds is needed and, to this end, the European Network Against Racism (ENAR) has recently published an elections’ analysis on ethnic minorities in the new European Parliament 2019-2025.¹⁶⁹

¹⁶² Share Network (2022) ‘Our approach’, Available at: <https://www.share-network.eu> [Accessed in 08/2022]

¹⁶³ ICMPD (2022) ‘MC2CM’, Available at: <https://www.icmpd.org/our-work/projects/mc2cm> [Accessed in 09/22]

¹⁶⁴ Eurocities (na) ‘Partners’, Available at: <https://eurocities.eu/partners/> [Accessed on 13/09/2022]

¹⁶⁵ See for instance the network “Rumourless cities” promoted by URBACT, whose description is available at: <https://urbact.eu/rumourless-cities>

¹⁶⁶ European Commission (2022) ‘Inclusion of Migrants and Refugees. Part of Urban Agenda for the EU’, Available at: <https://futurium.ec.europa.eu/en/urban-agenda/inclusion-migrants-and-refugees> [Accessed on 15/09/2022]

¹⁶⁷ Urban Agenda of the EU (2018) ‘Urban Academy of the Urban Agenda’, Available at: <https://ec.europa.eu/futurium/en/inclusion-migrants-and-refugees/urban-academy-integration.html> [Accessed on 23/11/2022]

¹⁶⁸ Ahmed, S. (2017) *Living a feminist life*. Durham: Duke University Press.

¹⁶⁹ ENAR (2019) ‘ENAR’S ELECTION ANALYSIS – ETHNIC MINORITIES IN THE NEW EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT 2019-2025’, Available at: <https://www.enar-eu.org/enar-s-election-analysis-ethnic-minorities-in-the-new-european-parliament-2019/> [Accessed in 08/2022]

4.2 Leadership, communication and coordination of participation

Box 5

Q: I want to be more aware of opportunities for participation in policy-making: what do I follow?

A: The European Website on Integration is probably the friendliest portal, and is accessible [here](#). Alternatively, they send regular newsletters for which you can subscribe [here](#). DG-Home has its own portal too, available [here](#), as well as a bi-monthly newsletter for which you can subscribe [here](#).

You can also check with your national contact point. For instance, those based in Portugal can turn to the High-Commissioner for Migrations' [portal](#), or subscribe to their newsletter at the bottom of [this page](#).

At local levels, organisations supporting migrants usually disseminate news on this issue: check out who is closest to where you live, and stay tuned.

Consider social media too! All of them are on Facebook and Twitter.

4.2.1 Do decision makers actively promote participation of residents irrespective of their nationality?

Participation of residents irrespective of nationality is actively promoted. For EU nationals living in another EU country, participation is promoted to raise awareness of opportunities to take part at various levels. In terms of voting rights: in the European elections, if they are registered and live in another EU country, they can either vote for candidates standing in their home country, or vote for candidates standing in the host country (they can vote only once); in municipal elections, they have the right to vote and in some countries to stand as a candidate, too.¹⁷⁰ Besides voting rights, EU nationals are consulted through a range of tools we describe in other sections (including Futurium and the Conference on the Future of Europe), and a large majority of technicians working in EU institutions are themselves EU free movers.

For TCNs, the right to vote for the European Parliament is not provided, although in some EU countries (for instance, Belgium¹⁷¹ and The Netherlands¹⁷²) they can vote for municipal elections under certain circumstances. However, we have described in the section above a range of networks, expert groups and advisory boards which include TCNs as individual members, or civil society organisations representing the interests of TCNs.

¹⁷⁰ Your Europe (2022) 'Help and advice for EU nationals and their family', Available at: https://europa.eu/youreurope/citizens/index_en.htm [Accessed on 19/09/2022]

¹⁷¹ Vlaanderen (2022) 'Elections in Belgium', Available at: <https://www.vlaanderen.be/en/elections-in-belgium> [Accessed on 19/09/2022]

¹⁷² Government of the Netherlands (n/a) 'Voting in municipal elections', Available at: <https://www.government.nl/topics/elections/voting-in-municipal-elections> [Accessed on 19/09/2022]

4.2.2 Does the EU use migrant-specific communication channels to make the case for participation among (and to reach) migrant communities? What communication channels are used to make the case for participation? How are residents informed about the possibility to participate? Does the EU use diverse communication methods to inform residents about the possibility to participate?

Institutional communication channels are used and reach migrant-specific channels indirectly. Call for expert groups are registered on the ec.europa.eu website, under the “Register of Commission Expert Groups and Other Similar Entities”, and then disseminated through a press release, and a network of institutions, including governmental entities making migration and integration policies, registered migrant-led organisations, civil society organisations dealing with migration and integration matters, and education institutions. Public consultations are registered under ec.europa.eu/eusurvey, disseminated too through a press release and a similar network of institutions. They are available in all EU official languages.

An interviewed member of one of the expert groups believes that access to those so-called “public” calls mostly circulate among a circle of people close to EU policy-making, and hardly reach a wider pool of potential candidates, indicating that networks are key to accessing these consultation forums (interview 6). Shaza Al Rihawi, a former member of EMAB, shares the same opinion – she knew about the possibility to participate because she was already involved in European affairs and particularly active on migrants’ inclusion (interview 4).

As for refugee activist Nour Machlah, he was contacted by the High Commission for Migration in Portugal, a nation-wide governmental organisation dealing with all migration-related matters, which encouraged him to apply to become an expert of the European Migration Advisory Board (EMAB) (interview 1; interview 2). The same is true for individuals with a migrant background who participate in the European Parliament’s Committees’ hearings; they are generally people already interested and involved in advocacy activities and European affairs (interview 5).

There are many communication channels used to make the case for participation, including dissemination of calls for participation. The **European Website on Integration** (EWSI) is one portal¹⁷³, with a wide-reaching mailing list. DG-HOME also has a newsroom and a bi-monthly newsletter. In each MS, registered institutions and individuals - including governmental entities making migration and integration policies, registered migrant-led organisations, civil society organisations dealing with migration and integration matters, and education institutions - receive information through EWSI, or through other networks such as the Inclusion Partnership of the EU Urban Agenda. They then disseminate it to a range of national and local partners. An agent of the Portugal High-Commission for

¹⁷³ EWSI was created after the Hague Programme (2005) and consists of a network of national coordinators from all MS, contracted by the Migration Policy Group (DG-HOME outsources the management of the Website). Each country coordinator collects and uploads information regarding migration integration in the respective MS (interview 3).

Migration explained that such information from the EC would usually be published on their website and on their social media (Facebook), and then disseminated through a wide network of partners including municipalities, civil society and migrant-led organisations, and universities (interview 2). Residents are possibly informed through national or local channels, notably through organisations and individuals receiving the messages disseminated through mailing lists.

In sum, dissemination of information about the possibility to participate occurs through various channels, either news of the official websites, newsletters sent to mailing lists open to subscription, social media (Facebook and Twitter) and then national contact points and their networks.

4.2.3 Is intersectionality considered in communication?

Intersectionality is not considered explicitly in communication (apart from the availability of information in EU official languages). An expert even suggested that taking part in participation processes requires time, and an occupation for which regular participation is possible and not disruptive. Oftentimes, participants in boards and expert groups are either civil servants, academics or consultants who can bear the weight of these unpaid meetings and the preparation before them (interview 6).

4.2.4 Does the EU communicate the results of consultations to residents? How are the results of a consultation process and its responses communicated to residents?

Results of all EU consultations on various matters should be made available to the public online, and in all official languages. Indeed, the European Commission allows the follow-up of public consultations through its portal, where it is also possible to subscribe to receive notifications about them.¹⁷⁴ Looking specifically at the migration and integration policy, the results of all consultations and minutes of expert groups are available on ec.europa.eu as PDF documents. The “Ask the People” consultation results, conducted by EMAB under the Urban Agenda for the EU, is available online. For the purpose of drafting the new 2021-2027 Action Plan, the results of its public consultation are published online, showing that 63% of the 800 respondents to the consultation were individuals, with 6% only TCNs.¹⁷⁵ In general, it does seem that the EU complies with its commitment to make results of consultations available online, but not necessary in all EU languages.

4.2.5 Does the EU produce information about consultations in different languages? – Who produces the information and in which languages is it provided?

¹⁷⁴ European Commission (2022) ‘Consultations’, Available at: https://ec.europa.eu/info/consultations_en [Accessed on 25/11/2022]

¹⁷⁵ European Commission (2020) ‘Analysis of the responses to the public consultation on the integration and inclusion of migrants and people with a migrant background’, Available at: https://ec.europa.eu/home-affairs/system/files_en?file=2020-11/synthesis_analysis_responses_public_consultation_integration_inclusion_2020.pdf [Consulted in 06/2022]

Information about consultations at the EU level is produced in different languages. Every document should be published in all 24 languages of the EU. We have not come across documents produced in other languages (such as Chinese or Arabic).

4.2.6 Is there a coordination mechanism in place to ensure that participation of all residents is actively promoted and communicated effectively?

To the best of our knowledge, there is no coordination mechanism at the EU level to ensure that participation of all residents is actively promoted and communicated effectively. However, the EU has an obligation to communicate calls and results, and it also uses the webpage https://ec.europa.eu/migrant-integration/home_en to collect and communicate EU's work and funds as well as country's facts and best practices.

4.3 Equal access

Box 6

Q: I want to participate in EU migration and integration policy-making: what are my options?

A: If you are an EU citizen, no matter where you live, you have the right to vote for EU Parliament.

You have the right to petition the European Parliament. A Webpage exists for this purpose only: <https://www.europarl.europa.eu/petitions/en/home>. And you can even lodge a complaint to the EU, through the European Ombudsman. Look it up here: <https://www.ombudsman.europa.eu/en/>.

You can propose legislation through the European Citizens' Initiative: <https://europa.eu/citizens-initiative/en>.

There are platforms dedicated to discuss EU policies. Here are a few: [Have your say](#); [Fit for Future](#); [Futurium](#). Although the Conference on the Future of Europe ended in May 2022, there might be follow-ups¹⁷⁶ so, keep in tune!

Check out the opportunities to become an expert, for instance in the expert groups and boards dedicated to migration and integration-related matters. Calls are published here: <https://ec.europa.eu/transparency/expert-groups-register/screen/calls-application?lang=en>.

4.3.1 Does the EU use diverse platforms to enable participation? Do all residents have an equal chance to make their voices heard?

¹⁷⁶ European Commission (2022) 'Conference on the Future of Europe', Available at https://ec.europa.eu/info/strategy/priorities-2019-2024/new-push-european-democracy/conference-future-europe_en [Accessed on 16/09/2022]

Several mechanisms exist at the EU level to enable EU citizens to participate in policy making and to make claims using diverse platforms. Indeed, the EU citizenship also entails the right to:

- petition to the **European Parliament** on an EU-related policy which directly affects citizens.¹⁷⁷ As Article 227 of the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union states, the right to petition is open to any EU citizen and any natural or legal person that is resident or has a registered office in a Member State, either individually or in association with others. It is worth to note that the petition has to be written in one of the official EU languages.
- complain to the **European Ombudsman**, whose role is to investigate complaints about poor administration by the EU institutions or other bodies. Complaints may be lodged by citizens or residents of EU countries or by EU-based associations or businesses.
- launch or support a **European citizens' initiative**, asking the European Commission to propose legislation. Once an initiative has reached 1 million signatures, the Commission will decide what to do. In order to launch an initiative it is essential to set up a group of organisers of at least 7 EU citizens living in 7 different EU countries. The European Citizens' Initiative (ECI) Forum offers support throughout the process. It is interesting to mention the 2018 ECI "We are a welcoming Europe, let us help!"¹⁷⁸, giving suggestions to European governments on how to overcome difficulties in managing migratory flows directed towards Europe.
- contact and receive a response from any EU institution in one of the EU's 24 official languages.

Finally, there are several platforms that serve the objective of giving voice to citizens, residents and stakeholders. Specifically, the **Have Your Say Platform**¹⁷⁹ and the **Fit for Future Platform**,¹⁸⁰ through which citizens, businesses and stakeholders can share their views on new EU policies and existing laws, and be notified and updated on published initiatives of the Commission, closed and open consultations. **Futurium**¹⁸¹ is another platform where several groups work on different topics and citizens can inform policy-making. One of these groups focuses on the Inclusion of Migrants and Refugees.

European residents have free access to these platforms, with no limits regarding citizenship. It seems that the residence status is required in theory, but not in practice,

¹⁷⁷ European Parliament (2022) 'The right to petition. Fact Sheets on the European Union', Available at: <https://www.europarl.europa.eu/factsheets/en/sheet/148/the-right-to-petition> [Accessed on 15/09/2022]

¹⁷⁸ European Citizens' initiative (n/a) 'We are a welcoming Europe, let us help!', Available at: https://europa.eu/citizens-initiative/initiatives/details/2018/000001_en [Accessed in 09/2022]

¹⁷⁹ Available here: https://ec.europa.eu/info/law/better-regulation/have-your-say_en

¹⁸⁰ Available here: https://ec.europa.eu/info/law/better-regulation/have-your-say-simplify_en

¹⁸¹ Available here: <https://futurium.ec.europa.eu/en>

meaning that one can register and access the participative processes without having to show a proof of residency/citizenship. All these participative processes are accessible online. One must register on the official EU platform with an email address. However, several factors may hinder equal access for some groups; for instance, the issue of digital divide, digital illiteracy, and the limits of the 24 EU official languages.

At the occasion of the **Conference on the Future of Europe** - a joint effort of the main EU institutions, namely the Commission, the Parliament and the Council - the EU launched a multilingual platform¹⁸² to help citizens participate directly in this year-long series of debates and discussions centred on ten key topics. This platform was available in the 24 official languages of the EU. The final report of the conference was presented in May 2022 and the platform offers an opportunity to keep updated with the follow-up of the proposals by the European institutions. It is important to note that the participation in the 4 European Citizens' Panels (number 4 was on migration) was limited to EU citizens.¹⁸³

4.3.2 Can migrants, refugees and asylum seekers access these platforms taking into account their specific circumstances?

Migrants' access to different civic participation platforms mentioned earlier depends on each specific case, on their legal status and knowledge of one of the 24 EU official languages. In the case of the **Expert Group on the views of migrants**¹⁸⁴, persons of migrant background, refugees and asylum seekers may apply to participate but they need to have a status that allows them to travel from one EU Member state to another and to have a sufficient level of English language skill (this appears in the frequently asked questions of EMAB, expert groups, consultations). Yet, from interviews, we gather that experts are targeted beforehand because they are already important and known through their activism or associative roles (interview 1; interview with a regular expert, 30/09/2022, online). In that sense, the composition of boards and expert groups is not accidental, with the same persons being involved across various groups, hence reducing the true representation of migrant communities. In the case of **EMAB**, Shaza Al Rihawi stated the existence of some obstacles to equal access, such as the lack of language sensitivity, since a good level of English is needed, and the use of jargon accessible only to well-educated people, or experts on the topic (interview 4).

It is interesting to note the existence of some specific trans-European pilot projects - supported by EU funding and in partnership with universities, research centres, local

¹⁸² Conference on the Future of Europe (2022), Available at: <https://futureu.europa.eu/?locale=en> [Accessed on 15/09/2022]

¹⁸³ Conference on the Future of Europe (2022) 'The European Citizens' Panels: questions and answers', Available [here](#) [Accessed on 10/09/2022]

¹⁸⁴ European Commission (2020) 'Register of Commission expert groups and other similar entities- Expert group on the views of migrants in the field of migration, asylum and integration', Available at: <https://ec.europa.eu/transparency/expert-groups-register/screen/expert-groups/consult?lang=en&groupId=3734&fromMeetings=true&meetingId=40774> [Accessed on 19/09/2022]

institutions - aimed at either (1) facilitating the migrant population's participation in local administration and politics, or (2) including migrants as key actors and not only final beneficiaries.

For the first case:

- "Empowering Immigrants' EU Social and Civic Participation through Innovative Media and Education"¹⁸⁵ is a project aimed at supporting the integration process of people with a migrant background via innovative educational tools, which will help them gain access to information and get a better understanding of issues that are most pertinent, including their rights and obligations in their host country.
- In terms of providing correct and accessible information on the various initiatives put in place at the EU level, the "EU Solidarity with Ukraine" platform¹⁸⁶ set up by DG HOME is a good example of an instrument which allows refugees from Ukraine to easily access information related to their rights and opportunities.

For the second case:

- MICADO project¹⁸⁷ (pilot in Antwerp, Bologna, Hamburg and Madrid), which has created a new solution to support migrant integration. The solution exploits existing and new data to design digital services for the use of public administrations, engaged civic society, migrants and refugees.

4.3.3 Are these diverse platforms of participation proactively communicated to diverse groups of residents? Is it visible and known to all communities how they can participate? Are their specific concerns considered?

Migrant participation in various platforms and initiatives for civic participation often depends on their proactive approach and the activation of existing European and cross-national networks working on the same issues. Moreover, much depends on the engagement and the political will and direction of local administrations. As a result, only people who are already interested in the topic try to find opportunities to make their voices heard at the institutional level, since there is no clear mechanism in place to include migrants and refugees (interview 4), or to proactively communicate existing opportunities to them. Importantly, there are some initiatives by civil society organisations whose goal is to bridge the local, European and global levels, making important information available and accessible to migrants and refugees. An example is

¹⁸⁵ IEUME (2022) 'Empowering Immigrants' EU Social and Civic Participation', Available at: <https://www.ieume.com/en/> [Accessed on 15/09/2022]

¹⁸⁶ European Commission (2022) 'EU solidarity with Ukraine', Available at: https://ec.europa.eu/info/strategy/priorities-2019-2024/stronger-europe-world/eu-solidarity-ukraine_en [Accessed on: 15/09/2022]

¹⁸⁷ European Commission (2022) 'Migrant Integration Cockpits and Dashboards. MICADO project', Available at: <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/822717> [Accessed on 15/09/2022]

the European Coalition of Migrants and Refugees (EU-COMAR), an association of European-based refugee, migrant and diaspora-led groups and initiatives (interview 4).¹⁸⁸

The specific concerns of migrant communities are often linked to particular national contexts. In an interview with Nour Machlah, he explained that when he joined EMAB, he advocated more for housing rights for refugees because this was the most pressing issue in Portugal where he lived and was actively involved in refugee reception. However, his colleagues raised other concerns, matching with the most pressing needs in their country (interview 1). As mentioned earlier, extended invitations by MEPs to speak of these issues publicly are not followed by legislative proposals.

4.4 Institutional links and responsiveness

4.4.1 *Is there a fully established mechanism in place to ensure that public institutions respond and incorporate the migrant voice in their decision making processes?*

There is a partially established mechanism ensuring the incorporation of the migrant voice in decision making.

A public consultation on the integration and social inclusion of migrants was held between July and October 2020 which fed into the 2021-2027 Action Plan. 6% of the 541 responses received came from non-EU citizens.¹⁸⁹ If this seems fairly in line with the proportion of non-EU citizens in the EU, we consider it low for a plan which concerns them primarily. The Action Plan, as stated before, also provides the creation of the Expert group on the views of migrants in the field of migration, asylum and integration. Consulting the FAQs page of the expert group's webpage, it is stated that before the set up of this group in 2020 there was no fully established mechanism to regularly consult migrants on issues that directly concern them at the EU level.

At the level of the European Parliament, as MEP Majorino first stated (interview 5), Committees regularly organise hearings - decided by the Presidency of the Committees in coordination with the coordinators of political groups of the related Committee - with groups from the civil society, which also include voices of people advocating for migrants' rights and/or migrants themselves. The EP hearings are a mechanism of listening to the civil society, which means that a follow up is not granted. In addition, the participation of MEPs in these hearings is not mandatory, but still strongly encouraged by their political groups. In line with this, some EMAB's members - as Shaza Al Rihawi and Nour El Machlah interviewed for MILE - were heard and consulted. Shaza Al Rihawi recalls she was heard by the LIBE Committee in relation to the New Pact. At that occasion, its stances were supported by some MEPs from Greece and Italy, the countries who were more interested

¹⁸⁸ The European Coalition of Migrants and Refugees is the European chapter of the Global Refugee Network (GRN). More information is available at: <https://www.europeancoalition.org>.

¹⁸⁹ European Commission (2020) 'Analysis of the responses to the public consultation on the integration and inclusion of migrants and people with a migrant background', Available at: https://home-affairs.ec.europa.eu/system/files_en?file=2020-11/synthesis_analysis_responses_public_consultation_integration_inclusion_2020.pdf [Accessed on 11/09/2022].

in the arrival of migrants (interview 4). Second, the interviewed MEP stated that in their daily work as individuals, MEPs get in contact with - or are contacted by - groups and networks of migrants, especially from the national context of reference of the MEP. However, these informal forms of institutional interaction largely depend on MEPs' sensitivity, will and interests in the topic. In summary, at the EP level, there is no stable and regular practice, nor fully established mechanisms, to ensure institutional responsiveness to migrants' requests (interview 5).

A study by the European Programme for Integration and Migration (EPIM)¹⁹⁰ found that migrants' engagement in EU policy making is often limited to recommendations without any follow-up. Moreover, unclear policymaking processes and coordination between different tiers of government (from the European to the local, through to the national one) hinder the flow of information to migrant-led initiatives.¹⁹¹ The interviews conducted with EMAB members, or former members, supported this statement (interview 1; interview 4).

In addition, larger civil society organisations seem to think they know the best way to assist migrants, and as a result, migrant advocates are often underestimated and used as volunteers as opposed to regular staff and experts: if this allows them to be active, their lack of stability and visibility in the organisations mainly represents an obstacle to influence policies and participation in decision-making. As EPIM's report states, "migrant-led organisations and migrant individuals do not possess sufficient networks and spaces to build strategies both among themselves and within mainstream organisations". As a consequence, "migrant-led organisations lack both the recognition and organisational capacity to influence EU policy makers' decision-making on issues affecting migrants".¹⁹²

Yet, some other mechanisms are worth mentioning. First, migrants participate in trade unions. The **Union Migrant Network**,¹⁹³ launched in 2015, comprises a network of trade union contact points across the EU where new arrivals and their families can obtain information and support on issues like employment, documentation, housing and integration. In 2020, it was officially integrated into the European Trade Union Confederation (ETUC), which represents the European workers, calling for actions and responding to calls for consultations by the European Commission. Second, **PICUM**¹⁹⁴ (Platform for International Cooperation on undocumented migrants) is an association whose members include various human rights organisations, migrants' rights

¹⁹⁰ EPIM (2019) 'Migrant-led advocacy across Europe. Challenges and Opportunities', Available at: <https://www.epim.info/wp-content/uploads/2019/11/Migrant-led-advocacy-across-Europe-Report.pdf> [Accessed on 25/09/2022]. The European Programme for Integration and Migration (EPIM) is an initiative of private foundations who have the aim of strengthening the role of civil society in building inclusive communities and developing humane and sustainable responses to migration. Here for further information on EPIM: <https://epim.info>.

¹⁹¹ *Ibid.*, p. 19.

¹⁹² *Ibid.*, p. 32-33.

¹⁹³ Union Migrant Net (2022), Available at: <https://www.unionmigrantnet.eu> [Accessed on 15/09/2022]

¹⁹⁴ PICUM (2022), 'Our vision', available at <https://picum.org/mission-vision-working-principles/> [Accessed on 21/11/2022]

organisations, migrant-led and other groups. The association works towards social justice and human rights for undocumented migrants.

4.4.2 Are migrants consulted on key policy spheres such as housing, education, health and employment? On which issues are migrants consulted?

To the best of our knowledge, migrants are consulted by DG HOME on policies directly related to migration and integration. It is interesting to note how in policies related to fields such as housing, education, health and employment, migrants are included and mentioned, but only as beneficiaries.¹⁹⁵ EMAB was consulted by DG HOME and DG EMPL, specifically on qualification and skills certificates (interview 4). At the level of the European Parliament, LIBE and DEVE Committees have heard voices representing migrants' interests and/or people with a migrant background themselves (interview 4; interview 5).

4.4.3 To what degree are migrants represented in the EU's consultative bodies, committees and issue-based groups? Are migrants involved in consultative bodies for key policy spheres?

Two bodies in particular have set as a priority the representation of TCNs: EMAB of the inclusive partnership and the 2020 Expert Group on the views of migration, asylum and integration with the EC.

4.4.4 Can migrants set their own agenda or are the issues pre-selected by the EU?

In these consultations, the setting of the agenda varies. According to EMAB representatives, "Two Board meetings and trainings (5-9 March, 2018 Brussels and 14-18 May, 2018 Amsterdam) contributed to shaping the Board's common vision."¹⁹⁶ EMAB member Nour Machlah recalls that issues were discussed by the group members themselves and translated into a vision (interview 1) whereas EMAB former member Shawa Al Rihawi explained that EMAB members studied the agenda of the European Commission and chose some topics to work on, through study visits to various cities as well as meetings with different DGs (interview 4). Living in Portugal, the main issue Nour Machlah wished to tackle was refugees' housing access.

Experiences in other expert groups vary: For the European Integration Network, DG-Home initiates the agenda for the bi-annual encounters of country coordinators (interview 2), while these country coordinators can present good practices of their choice. As for other expert groups such as the one on economic migration, it is the DG HOME that presents proposals to be discussed/commented on by the experts (interview 6).

¹⁹⁵ European Commission (2022) 'Inclusion of non-EU migrants - Employment, Social affairs and Inclusion', Available at: <https://ec.europa.eu/social/main.jsp?catId=1274&langId=en> [Accessed on 15/09/2022]

¹⁹⁶ European Commission (2018) 'European Migrant Advisory Board', Available at: <https://ec.europa.eu/futurium/en/inclusion-migrants-and-refugees/european-migrant-advisory-board-emab.html> [Accessed on 13/09/2022]

4.4.5 Are provisions in place to ensure that participation structures, such as consultative bodies, can feed into the mainstream policy process of relevant public authorities and get a considered and timely response?

EMAB member Nour Machlah recalls in an interview that the issues raised by the Advisory Board were indeed presented in various parliamentary sessions, meetings with MEPs, in DG-Home meetings and so on. Yet, in his opinion, the chance for them to be considered into the policy process were slim, since proposals were not adopted by parties, shaped into policy proposals, and brought to a vote (interview 1). This corroborates elements of interview with other EMAB member Shawa Al Rihawi. Hence the impact of EMAB in shaping policy has been limited.

4.5 Support for community self-organisation

4.5.1 Do the EU institutions work with migrant associations?

Firstly, it is important to note that generally, in the management of migration flows, EU collaborates with other relevant international organisations: United Nations (UN), including the UNHCR and the International Organisation for Migration (IOM), the International Centre for Migration Policy Development (ICMPD), the OECD (the Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development), the UN High-level Dialogue on International Migration and Development and the Global Forum on Migration and Development.¹⁹⁷ Additionally, EU institutions work with migrant associations, mainly through consultations and the creation of expert groups mentioned earlier.

To understand how the EU works with migrant associations, we have explored if and how migrant-led organisations create an intra-European network among them and whether they are part of EU-level or international-level umbrella organisations. According to research conducted in 2019 by EPIM,¹⁹⁸ migrants' advocates encounter difficulties in coordinating their efforts and claim a lack of opportunities to network. In mentioning a strong desire to broaden the extent of coordination among different organisations working in the same field, the study also highlights the risk of competition - instead of collaboration - among them; for example, groups within the same migrant community. Since not much is known about how migrants are able to associate across different EU countries, in 2021, EWSI conducted research to map key migrant-led organisations across the EU.¹⁹⁹ Among these organisations, we can find refugee-led, migrant-led, migrant women-led, second generation / youth-led, and other migration-related diversity. On a

¹⁹⁷ European Commission (2022) 'Migration and Home affairs. Collaboration with international organisations', Available at: https://home-affairs.ec.europa.eu/policies/international-affairs/collaboration-international-organisations_en [Accessed on 20/09/2022]

¹⁹⁸ EPIM (2019) 'Migrant-led advocacy across Europe. Challenges and Opportunities', Available at: <https://www.epim.info/wp-content/uploads/2019/11/Migrant-led-advocacy-across-Europe-Report.pdf> [Accessed on 25/09/2022]

¹⁹⁹ European Commission European Website on Integration (2021) 'Mapping key migrant-led organisations across the EU', Available at: https://ec.europa.eu/migrant-integration/special-feature/mapping-key-migrant-led-organisations-across-eu_en [Accessed on 25/09/22]

national level, 35% of all these organisations represent the interests of many multi-ethnic and multi-migrant groups, whereas 28% of them cater to the interests of one ethnic or religious group; 15% represent the interests of multi-ethnic groups who gather together because of a specific interest (for example, being a woman). The general pattern of these data describing how people with a migrant background organise themselves was confirmed also for the local level by P. Majorino, who had directly worked on integration and inclusion policies for the city of Milan from 2011 to 2019 (interview 5).

Going back to the EWSI research study, only 25% of all migrant-led organisations within European countries are members of EU-level or international-level umbrella organisations. Some examples are the European Network against Racism (ENAR) with 10 organisations, the European Network of Migrant Women (ENoMW) with 7 structures. Interestingly, there are other important pan-EU or international organisations working on themes related to migration and integration, however, in most cases, they cannot be classified as migrant-led.

At the level of the European Parliament, MEPs interested in the topic build and maintain links with organisations representing the interests of people with a migrant background or involving migrants themselves, who are active at the local level (interview 5).

4.5.2 Does the EU administration support the self-organisation of migrant communities?

The EU, notably through the most recent Action Plan, does not directly support the self-organisation of migrants, but simply encourages partnerships, for instance with existing migrant-led or diaspora organisations. EU support for the self-organisation of migrants partly depends on national politics and bureaucratic realities. In general, associations - in comparison with organisations and organisations offering membership - are the most common form of self-organisation chosen by migrants.²⁰⁰ The study by EWSI mentioned before, states some concrete examples.²⁰¹ For instance, in Romania, migrants may be not able to organise and engage in policy-related work because of the Aliens Act forbidding the association of TCNs with the aim of setting up political parties or similar organisations. Conversely, in Estonia, migrants are more free to form associations. It is worth to note that at the moment there is not an exhaustive dataset of all migrant structures from across the EU: indeed, the European Website on Integration calls for help in drafting this list of migrant-led organisations and their experiences.

At the EU level, EWSI's study shows that if the ability of migrants to associate on the ground is limited, amplifying their voices at the EU level is even more difficult. As a consequence, it can be said that more attention should be given to the work of these self-led structures. It is with this goal that EWSI drafted a list -still not exhaustive- of national

²⁰⁰ *Ibid.*

²⁰¹ *Ibid.*

and local level migrant-led organisations in EU countries, calling for help in order to broaden it as much as possible.²⁰²

4.5.3 Are there funds or other support for organisational capacity building targeting migrants? Where does the funding come from and how sustainable are these funds in the longer term?

EU provides some funds and other kinds of support towards migrants' organisational capacity building. In the case of EMAB, for example, board members benefited from a secretariat, a trainer, as well as resources for travel expenses when face-to-face meetings with EMAB members were organised. The support also consisted in facilitating contacts with MEPs, regular information regarding on-going meetings on migration and asylum-related matters and other channels to include EMAB members in EU-level discussions (interview 1).

4.5.4 Does the EU administration support intercultural dialogue and exchange between communities?

Intercultural dialogue has long been a principle supported by EU institutions as well as by the Council of Europe, especially in the field of youth policy and education, multilingualism, culture and integration.

Youth. Indeed, the development of youth exchanges and the participation of young people in democratic life is encouraged and represents an important aspect of funding programmes for youth since the late 1980s. The attention of the European Commission on this has increased over the years and 'intercultural dialogue' has been clearly included in the 'Youth in Action' programme (2007-2013). The policy developments show an increased focus on intercultural dialogue at EU level and in the Council of Europe, which reached its peak in 2006 when the European Parliament and the EU Member States decided to declare 2008 the European Year of Intercultural Dialogue. According to the decision, intercultural dialogue is "at the heart of the European project and it is important to provide the means for intercultural dialogue and dialogue between citizens to strengthen respect for cultural diversity and deal with the complex reality in our societies and the coexistence of different cultural identities and beliefs".²⁰³ The 35-year-old EU youth mobility programme Erasmus, and then Erasmus +, is one example of how short-term migration and intercultural dialogue is tied together. The 2022 Erasmus + programme guide²⁰⁴ does include "intercultural dialogue" as part of the competences

²⁰² *Ibid.* The list can be found as a PDF document to be downloaded at this webpage: https://ec.europa.eu/migrant-integration/special-feature/mapping-key-migrant-led-organisations-across-eu_en.

²⁰³ Official Journal of the European Union (2006) 'Decision No 1983/2006/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 18 December 2006 concerning the European Year of Intercultural Dialogue (2008)', p. L412/44, Available at: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32006D1983&from=EN> [Accessed on 15/09/2022].

²⁰⁴ Erasmus+ (2022) 'Erasmus plus programme guide', Available at: https://erasmus-plus.ec.europa.eu/sites/default/files/2022-01/2022-erasmusplus-programme-guide-v2_en_0.pdf [Accessed on 13/09/2022]

acquired by beneficiaries to promote EU democracy. Erasmus+ also funds projects aiming at intercultural dialogue such as interculturality.eu.

Intercultural dialogue between migrants and native population. When it comes to the issues of migrants' inclusion and urban policies, the Council of Europe has been promoting intercultural dialogue through its programme "Intercultural Cities".²⁰⁵ Intercultural Cities is a network of cities across Europe dealing with reception and settlement of migrants, and interculturalism. Its work has been instrumental in the promotion of "intercultural policies": diversity arising from demographic heterogeneity, notably migration-based diversity, is seen as an asset for urban development and hence should be seized to increase the socio-economic contributions of migrant residents. These intercultural policies encompass a wide range of initiatives from support for recruitment of migrants to funding of intercultural artistic events. Scholars have understood the success of intercultural policies in the context of a backlash of multiculturalism.²⁰⁶ It relies on the promotion of a dialogue between communities, a two-way process involving both migrants and nationals; as well as an understanding of diversity as a lever for economic growth. Yet it is precisely its shortcomings: intercultural policies usually put a blind on more structural inequalities and the responsibility of integration shifts from government to individuals.²⁰⁷

It is interesting to note that the Council of Europe has been promoting intercultural dialogue in view of migrant integration, conflict prevention and reconciliation, whilst the EU has been focusing on the development of intercultural awareness and understanding of individuals, in view of European citizenship and mobility.²⁰⁸

4.6 Monitoring quality of participation schemes

4.6.1 Does the EU work with residents to improve activities promoted by its participation strategy at all levels, and to make it more effective?

Not to our knowledge.

4.6.2 Is there regular monitoring and evaluation of these participation activities?

When it comes to participation of residents, we do not know. For other initiatives, members of EMAB have stated that their meetings and activities, including consultations and advocacy, were monitored regularly to ensure consistency and quality. Meetings'

²⁰⁵ White, B. W. (2021) 'City-based inclusion networks in a post-multicultural world: the Intercultural Cities programme of the council of Europe', *Local Government Studies* 48(6): 1070-1090.

²⁰⁶ Phillimore, J., and Sigona, N. (Eds.) (2020) *Superdiversity, Policy and Governance in Europe: Multi-scalar Perspectives*. Policy Press.

²⁰⁷ Schiller, M. (2016) *European cities, municipal organizations and diversity: The new politics of difference*. Springer; Desille, A. (2019) 'Revisiting the diversity-urban development nexus: Perspectives from Israeli immigrant towns', *Political Geography* 73: 1-16.

²⁰⁸ Council of Europe (2022) 'Intercultural dialogue', Available at: <https://pjp-eu.coe.int/en/web/youth-partnership/intercultural-dialogue> [Consulted in 06/2022]

objectives, minutes, and activities developed were hence evaluated, but these evaluations are not published online and made available (interview 1).

4.6.3 Are the results of monitoring and evaluation publicised, and do they feed back into the process?

The results of the evaluation of EMAB activities are, to the best of our knowledge, not publicised. Following the interview with Nour Machlah, it seems that it is at the discretion of the members to use the feedback (interview 1). More generally, it is unknown whether any monitoring and evaluation outcomes of participation schemes more widely are publicised.

4.6.4 What mechanism is in place to check the procedures and impact of participation schemes on a regular basis?

The EU bureaucracy requires an agenda for meetings, minutes, report of activities and other documents, all feeding into a process of accountability that enables to monitor participation. Yet the procedures and impact of participation schemes are not monitored.

4.6.5 How are changes to the participation schemes being decided?

We do not know.

4.7 Resources for participation

Box 7

Q: I am part of a migrant-led group, and we have ideas: how do I get support?

A: We have listed the various EU funds created to support migration and integration-related actions:

- Asylum, Migration and Integration fund (AMIF): very wide array of issues, including implementation of the CEAS, integration measures, infrastructures, to voluntary returns and cooperation with third-countries.
- Cohesion's Action for Refugees in Europe (CARE): focus on providing the basic needs of people fleeing the Russian invasion of Ukraine; enhancing the administrative capacity of Member States to cater for the needs of refugees; and developing tailor-made solutions for the long-term integration of people with a migrant background. In October 2022, the Flexible Assistance to Territories (FAST-CARE) was adopted in order to offer further flexibility for the implementation of Cohesion Policy funding.²⁰⁹

²⁰⁹ European Commission (2022) 'Questions and Answers: Cohesion Policy steps up support to address the consequences of Russia's aggression in Ukraine with the 'Flexible Assistance to Territories', Available at: https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/en/QANDA_22_4044 [Accessed on 30/11/2022]

- European Social Fund Plus (ESF+) (until 2020, it was the European Social Fund, the EU Programme for Employment and Social Innovation (EaSI) and the Fund for European Aid to the Most Deprived (FEAD) but this new ESF includes them all): focus on “investing in people” in the following domains: EU’s employment, social, education and skills policies, including structural reforms in these areas
- European Regional Development Fund (ERDF): focus on strengthening economic, social and territorial cohesion in the European Union by correcting imbalances between its regions. Here the understanding is loose too, and includes urban development, social rights, digitisation and mobility
- Erasmus+: focus on education and training for youth (individuals and organisations)
- European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development (EAFRD): rural development programmes mostly, with an objective that might interest you, “achieving a balanced territorial development of rural economies and communities.”

Regularly check the call for actions of each of these funds through their official webpages (all hosted by <https://ec.europa.eu>). Funding opportunities at European and national levels are also registered on EWSI: https://ec.europa.eu/migrant-integration/funds-available-eu-level_en.

4.7.1 Is the value of participation in public decision making by all communities recognised by the EU?

The value of participation in public decision-making is generally recognised. Indeed, democracy is one of the foundations of the EU, and depends on giving citizens the opportunity to participate in public life and help shape laws and public policies. Criticised for lacking democratic legitimacy, the EU tried to find new ways to include citizens in decision-making: for instance, the above mentioned 2022 Conference on the Future of Europe²¹⁰ was an attempt to amplify EU citizens’ voices.

On some policies, the attention to public participation in decision making is higher than for others. On the theme of the environment, for example, provisions on public participation in decision-making by the European institutions can be found in Title III of the [Aarhus Regulation](#), and concern the preparation, modification or review of plans or programmes related to the environment.²¹¹ More specifically, the participation of

²¹⁰ European Commission (2022) ‘Conference on the Future of Europe’, Available at https://ec.europa.eu/info/strategy/priorities-2019-2024/new-push-european-democracy/conference-future-europe_en [Accessed on 16/09/2022]

²¹¹ Official Journal of the European Union (2006) ‘Regulation (EC) No 1367/2006 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 6 September 2006 on the application of the provisions of the Aarhus Convention on Access to Information, Public Participation in Decision-making and Access to Justice in Environmental Matters to Community institution and bodies’, Available at: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=OJ:L:2006:264:0013:0019:EN:PDF> [Accessed on 15/09/2022].

migrants in public decision-making is not recognised by the EU. Indeed, as MIPEX reveals, in most EU countries, foreign citizens are not enfranchised or regularly informed, consulted or involved in local civil society and public life. “Political participation is the weakest area of integration policy (25/100). Most immigrants are granted little opportunity to inform and improve the policies that affect them daily. They have limited local voting rights (non-EU citizens in the case of EU countries). They can rarely rely on strong consultative bodies or well-supported migrant organisations. Their political opportunities differ enormously from country to country.”²¹²

Moreover, the EU Agency for Human Rights has published in 2017 an interesting study on the promotion of the participation of migrants and their descendants, calling MS to increase the participation of migrants and their descendants in decision-making procedures affecting their lives, at a minimum through public consultation processes; giving voting/election rights at local and regional levels, and facilitating acquisition of citizenship.²¹³

4.7.2 Is there adequate budgeting for staff time and training to support and facilitate residents' participation?

Yes, through funding that is allocated following calls/tenders (and not directly at DG HOME). The Commission's proposals for the inclusion of TCNs foresee two main funding instruments aimed at migrants' inclusion in European societies: European Social Fund Plus (ESF+) with 101.2 billion Euro and the Asylum and Migration Integration Fund (AMIF) with 10.4 billion Euro. Moreover, there are some other EU programmes: the European Regional Development Fund (ERDF), the Erasmus + fund, the Rights and Values Fund.²¹⁴ Some of the resources within these funds are used for staff training to support participation of residents, yet there is no fully established mechanism at DG-Home.

4.7.3 Are grant programmes used to support residents in creating stable, inclusive activities and structures that can strengthen civic and political participation for the long term?

It is important to recall that funds, such as AMIF, directed at integration matters do not directly reach local and regional governments and NGOs, who are at the frontline of welcoming new residents, and foreign residents' integration policies (interview 4). Despite what we stated earlier in this report as a “local turn”, and although municipalities have been vocal on this topic - especially at the time of the Syrian and later Afghan refugee crisis -, integration funds' management stays in the hands of national governments. Local

²¹² MIPEX (2020) ‘Migrant Integration Policy Index - Political participation’, Available at: <https://www.mipex.eu/political-participation> [Accessed on 15/09/2022]

²¹³ European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights (2017) ‘Together in the EU. Promoting the participation of migrants and their descendants’, Available at: https://fra.europa.eu/sites/default/files/fra_uploads/fra-2017-together-in-the-eu_en.pdf [Accessed on 15/09/2022]

²¹⁴ ECRE and PICUM (2019) ‘Policy Paper: Promoting socio-economic inclusion of migrants and refugees in the next EU budget (2021-2027)’, Available at: <https://ecre.org/wp-content/uploads/2019/02/PICUM-ECRE-Policy-Paper-Promoting-socio-economic-inclusion-of-migrants-and-refugees-in-the-next-EU-budget-December-2018.pdf> [Accessed on 15/09/2022]

authorities receive funds indirectly, depending on central government decision in allocating funds (interview 5). It is worth to mention that the response to the Ukrainian refugee crisis has triggered a change in relation to this.

4.7.4 Which resources does the EU invest in provisions for participation?

EU funding programmes outlined earlier can be used for promoting and supporting civic participation. This is the case of the MILE project here, funded by AMIF, as well as other projects we have mentioned throughout the report.

4.7.5 Are training opportunities for participants in place?

In the case of EMAB, training activities were organised for members of the board. Even after the end of this experience, some of the former members of EMAB have maintained contacts and links among themselves (interview 4). The MILE project also provides training of local authority and migrant-led organisation staff.

4.7.6 Is there a secretariat or a similar support structure to support participants?

Expert groups and boards are allocated a Brussels-based secretariat for support and technical organisation of activities.

4.8 Commitment to full political rights for all residents

4.8.1 Does the EU actively lobby for granting / extending full EU voting rights to their migrant population?

The EU partially lobbies for extending full EU voting rights to their migrant population. Since the 1970s, granting full voting rights in municipal elections to EU nationals and TCNs in the country of residence has been on the EU political agenda.²¹⁵

Firstly, EU citizenship - introduced in 1992 in the Treaty of Maastricht - grants all EU nationals residing in another Member State local voting rights in that state.²¹⁶

Regarding TCNs' voting rights, the EU has no legal authority to decide for binding EU rules on the voting rights of TCNs residing in one of its MS; the EU can only encourage MS to amend their national laws on this issue. The EU Treaties do not provide a legal basis for obliging Member States to grant voting rights or other political rights to resident TCNs. However, a majority of 14 of the 27 EU Member States allow some categories of resident TCNs to participate in local elections, according to a specific status and/or duration of residence as a requirement.²¹⁷ Granting voting rights at municipal and local elections to

²¹⁵ Groenendijk Kees (2008) 'Local Voting Rights for Non-Nationals in Europe: What We Know and What We Need to Learn', Available at: <https://www.migrationpolicy.org/research/local-voting-rights-non-nationals-europe-what-we-know-and-what-we-need-learn> [Accessed on 15/09/2022]

²¹⁶ Groenendijk Kees (2014) 'Voting rights for Nationals of Non-EU States' in Bundeszentrale für politische Bildung, Available at: <https://www.bpb.de/themen/migration-integration/kurz dossiers/184711/voting-rights-for-nationals-of-non-eu-states/> [Accessed on 15/09/2022]

²¹⁷ *Ibid.*

residents with a migrant background is the only way to grant them stable and formal mechanisms of political and institutional representation. In cities where it happened - as in Milan with the City Councilwoman Sumaya Abdel Qader from 2016-2021 - there are positive outcomes in terms of inclusion and multicultural policies (interview 5).

In relation to European elections, if you are an EU national living in another EU country, you have the right to vote and to stand as a candidate in European - as well as municipal - elections held in that country.²¹⁸ Conversely, the electoral act of the parliament does not provide voting rights for non-EU nationals.²¹⁹

From an institutional point of view, in November 2021, the European Commission adopted a package of measures to reinforce democracy and protect the integrity of elections: it includes two legislative proposals on the right to vote and stand as candidates of EU citizens residing in a different Member State from their state of origin in elections to the European Parliament and municipal elections, but no measure tackling the issue of TCNs.²²⁰

4.8.2 What channels does the EU use to make the case for extended political rights?

Looking at the concrete actions adopted to extend voting rights to TCNs in Europe, in 2020, the European Citizens' rights, Involvement and Trust (ECIT) Foundation - through "Citizens for Europe" (CFEU), a community of over 500 civil society organisations who work to have a more participative and democratic Europe - submitted a proposal asking the Commission to reform legislation related to voting rights in Europe, in order to extend the existing right to regional, national elections and referenda to EU citizens, without discriminating TCNs.²²¹

Political and voting rights, especially for national elections, are strictly connected to citizenship and national policies ruling on it, which vary significantly across EU countries: in many cases, second-generation migrants can face problems in obtaining it, and it is therefore interesting to investigate their actions and initiatives. As the above-mentioned EWSI study showed, across EU countries, there are many migrant-led organisations

²¹⁸ European Commission (2022) 'Citizens' Rights', Available at: https://ec.europa.eu/info/aid-development-cooperation-fundamental-rights/your-rights-eu/know-your-rights/citizens-rights_en [Accessed on 15/09/2022]. Here, you can find the explication of Chapter 5 of the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights which protects the right to vote and stand as a candidate at elections to the European Parliament, and the right to vote and to stand as a candidate at municipal elections, among other rights.

²¹⁹ Consolidated text: Council Decision of 25 June and 23 September 2002 amending the Act concerning the election of the representatives of the European Parliament by direct universal suffrage, annexed to Decision 76/787/EEC, EEC, Euratom (2002/772/EC, Euratom), Available at: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A02002D0772-20020923> [Accessed on 15/09/2022]

²²⁰ European Commission (2021) 'Democracy and electoral rights', Available at: https://ec.europa.eu/info/policies/justice-and-fundamental-rights/eu-citizenship/democracy-and-electoral-rights_en [Accessed on 15/09/2022]

²²¹ Citizens for Europe (2020) 'ECI- Full Political Rights for EU Citizens', Available at: <https://www.citizensforeurope.eu/proposals/eci-full-political-rights-for-eu-citizens> [Accessed on 15/09/2022]

headed by children of migrants or youth leaders, which are active in offering educational support and often work lobbying for better access to rights.²²² The study mentions some concrete examples of second-generation organisations who advocate for wider citizenship rights at a national level, but the contacts and networks among organisations in different MS are not so evident. However, in 2020, the European University Institute has published a report which examines the development of birthright citizenship across the EU MS during the 2013-2020 period. According to this study, more general provisions should be made for children of migrants who are born and will live in a state in order to facilitate migrants' integration.²²³

²²² European Commission European Website on Integration (2021) 'Mapping key migrant-led organisations across the EU', Available at: https://ec.europa.eu/migrant-integration/special-feature/mapping-key-migrant-led-organisations-across-eu_en [Accessed on 25/09/22]

²²³ European Website on Integration (2020) 'Trends in Birthright Citizenship in EU 28 (2013-2020)', Available at: https://ec.europa.eu/migrant-integration/library-document/trends-birthright-citizenship-eu-28-2013-2020_en [Accessed on 25/09/2022].

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Eurocities / Migration Work (2014) *Integrating Cities Toolkit: Managing diversity and promoting equality in cities administration and service provision.*

Garcés-Mascreñas, B. and R. Penninx (2016) *Integration Processes and Policies in Europe: Contexts, Levels and Actors*, Springer Open (eBook)

Igualtats Connect (2019) *Toolkit to incorporate intersectionality into local policies.*

²²⁴ The research conducted as part of this project was informed by these sources, providing a framework for evaluating existing integration, equality, diversity and civic participation policy and practice.

APPENDIX – List of primary data sources

1. Interview with N. Machlah, 08/09/2022, Lisbon
2. Interview with the Head of international relations of the High Commission for Migration, Portugal, 16/09/2022, phone
3. Interview with a country coordinator for EWSI, 19/09/2022, phone
4. interview with S. Al Rihawi, 27/09/2022, online
5. Interview with P. Majorino, 28/09/2022, online
6. Interview with a regular expert, 30/09/2022, online